

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

Project Acronym:	VITALISE
Project Title:	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
Project Number:	101007990
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme INFRAIA-02-2020 Integrating Activities for Starting Communities
Type of Action:	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Start date of the Project:	April 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

D4.8 Commercialisation Potential of Research Results

(Version 3.0 31/03/2022)

Disclaimer: The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability.

Copyright message: ©VITALISE Consortium, 2021. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

D4.8 Commercialization Potential of Research Results

Deliverable:	D4.8 Boosting Commercialisation Potential of Research Results	
Work Package:	WP4 Capacity Building and Training	
Due Date:	M12 - 31/03/2022	
Submission Date:	31.03.2022	
Lead Beneficiary:	AV	
Version:	3.0	
Status:	Final Version	
Author name(s):	Dr. Paraskevi Giourka, Adriane Thrash, Argyris Spyridis, Lamprini Kiosse, Elena Gagani, Christos Gaganis.	
Contributor(s):	ENOLL, TREBAG, VICOM, CERTH, SIT, UPM, WITA, VILABS, LLSA	
Reviewer(s):	Francesca Spagnoli (ENoLL)	Ada Pellumbaj (VILABS)
Approved by:	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL), Project Coordinator	
Keywords:	Innovation Management, Exploitation, Sustainability	
Nature:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R – Report <input type="checkbox"/> P – Prototype <input type="checkbox"/> D – Demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> O - Other	
Dissemination level:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

The **VITALISE** Consortium consists of:

Participant #	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW	ENoLL	Belgium
2	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Greece
3	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	LAUREA	Finland
4	THOMAS MORE KEMPEN VZW	LICALAB	Belgium
5	FUNDACION INTRAS	INTRAS	Spain
6	TREBAG SZELLEMI TULAJDON- ES PROJEKTMENEDZSER KORLATOLT FELELOSSEGU TARSASAG	TREBAG	Hungary
7	ASOCIACION DE INDUSTRIAS DE CONOCIMIENTO Y TECNOLOGIA - GAIA - EUSKALHERRIKO EZAGUTZA ETA TEKNOLOGIA INDUSTRIEN ELKARTEA	GAIA	Spain
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	VICOM	Spain
9	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	Greece
10	AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH	AIT	Austria
11	SOCIALIT SOFTWARE E CONSULTING SRL	SIT	Italy
12	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	Spain
13	WITA SRL	WITA	Italy
14	ANTHOLOGY VENTURES JSC	AV	Bulgaria
15	VILABS OE	VILABS	Greece
16	FORUM DES LIVING LABS EN SANTE ET AUTONOMIE	LLSA	France
17	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT INDHOVEN	TUE	Netherlands
18	ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSITY	McGill	Canada
19	UNIVERSITE DE MONTREAL	UDEM	Canada

D4.8 Commercialization Potential of Research Results

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	28.03.2022	AV	Revised by VILABS & ENOLL
0.2	31.03.2022	AV	Approved by ENoLL and AUTH

Table of Contents

LIST OF TABLES.....	6
LIST OF FIGURES	6
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	7
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1. INTRODUCTION.....	9
1.1 THE VITALISE PROJECT	9
1.2 PURPOSE AND SCOPE OF TASK 4.6 “BOOSTING COMMERCIALIZATION POTENTIAL”	9
1.3 RELATION TO OTHER WPS AND TASKS	10
1.4 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE	11
2 A REVIEW ON ACCELERATION BOOTCAMP TRAINING.....	11
2.1 DEFINITION OF THE TERM “BOOTCAMP”	11
2.2 INDICATIVE EXAMPLES THAT INSPIRED THE VITALISE ACCELERATION BOOTCAMPS	11
2.3 STRATEGIC FOCUS OF THE VITALISE ACCELERATION BOOTCAMPS	13
3 THE VITALISE PROJECT ACCELERATION BOOTCAMP	13
3.1 BOOTCAMP OUTLINE.....	14
3.2 RESEARCH TEAM SELECTION.....	16
3.3 RESEARCH TEAMS CO-PILOT MENTORS.....	16
3.4 TIME SCHEDULE AND TRAINING MATERIAL.....	16
4 MONITORING INNOVATION AND COMMERCIALISATION POTENTIAL: LITERATURE REVIEW AND OVERVIEW OF RELEVANT TOOLS.....	18
4.1 INNOVATION RADAR FRAMEWORK BACKGROUND	18
4.1.1 <i>Innovation Radar Survey</i>	18
4.1.2 <i>Innovation Potential Indicator</i>	19
4.1.3 <i>Innovator Capacity Indicator</i>	20
4.2 THE MARKET CREATION POTENTIAL INDICATOR - MCPI	20
4.3 THE KTH INNOVATION READINESS LEVEL	23
4.4 OTHER START UP ASSESSMENT TOOLS	25
5 VITALISE ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK ON THE INNOVATION POTENTIAL OF RESEARCH TEAMS IN TA IVA.....	26
5.1 SOCIETAL READINESS LEVEL	27
5.2 LEGAL READINESS LEVEL.....	28
5.2.1 <i>Application of the VITALISE adaptation to the KTH Innovation Readiness Framework</i>	29
5.2.2 <i>Role of AV and other partners in boosting commercialization potential</i>	30
6 MONITORING THE DEVELOPMENT OF TA INNOVATIONS.....	31
7 EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY PLAN.....	32
7.1 CREATING AND MAINTAINING THE RIGHT CONDITIONS FOR BOOSTING COMMERCIALIZATION POTENTIAL ..	32
7.2 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN	34
8 CONCLUSIONS, RISKS, AND NEXT STEPS	34
9 ANNEX A: INNOVATION RADAR QUESTIONNAIRE.....	36
10 ANNEX B: THE KTH INNOVATION READINESS LEVEL.....	40

List of Tables

TABLE 1 BOOTCAMP PROCESS AND CORE ELEMENTS	13
TABLE 2 ANALYSIS OF BOOTCAMP SCENARIO	15
TABLE 3 BOOTCAMP TEAMS SELECTION CRITERIA	16
TABLE 4. TIME SCHEDULE OF THE VITALISE BOOTCAMP	17
TABLE 5 MARKET CREATION POTENTIAL INDICATOR DECISION RULES	21
TABLE 6 SOCIETAL READINESS LEVEL	27
TABLE 7 LEGAL READINESS LEVEL	28
TABLE 8 TENTATIVE BOOTCAMP RISKS AND MITIGATION MEASURES	35
TABLE 9 CUSTOMER READINESS LEVEL	40
TABLE 10 TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL	41
TABLE 11 BUSINESS READINESS LEVEL	41
TABLE 12 IP READINESS LEVEL	43
TABLE 13 TEAM READINESS LEVEL	44
TABLE 14 FUNDING READINESS LEVEL	45

List of Figures

FIGURE 1. THE UNDERSTAND – REFLECT – ADAPT PRINCIPLES ADOPTED BY VITALISE	14
FIGURE 2. THE INNOVATION POTENTIAL INDICATOR AND INNOVATOR'S CAPACITY INDICATOR OF THE INNOVATION RADAR METHODOLOGY (SOURCE: INNOVATION RADAR: IDENTIFYING INNOVATIONS AND INNOVATORS WITH HIGH POTENTIAL IN ICT FP7, CIP & H2020 PROJECTS. JRC SCIENCE AND POLICY REPORT, 2015.)	19
FIGURE 3. THE KTH INNOVATION READINESS LEVEL	24
FIGURE 4 THE KTH INNOVATION READINESS LEVEL PROCESS	25
FIGURE 5. SUMMARY OF THE INNOVATION MANAGEMENT STRATEGY OF VITALISE PROJECT	29
FIGURE 6 TIME-PLAN OF THE INNOVATION AND COMMERCIALIZATION EVALUATION FRAMEWORK	32

List of Abbreviations

BRL	Business Readiness Level
CRL	Customer Readiness Level
DoW	Description of Work
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FRL	Funding Readiness Level
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
ICI	Innovation Capacity Indicator
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IPI	Innovation Performance Indicator
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IPRL	Intellectual Property Readiness Level
IR	Innovation Radar
IRL	Innovation Readiness Level
LLs	Living Labs
MCPI	Market Creation Potential
R&D	Research and Development
TA	Transnational Access
TCP	Team Co-Pilot
TmRL	Team Readiness Level
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Research conducted within the infrastructure and services offered by Living Labs (LLs) can lead to the production of a wide range of findings some of which have the potential to become competitive products or services of benefit to society. Commercialisation support activities are designed within VITALISE project with a purpose to increase the value of the research results produced in LLs from a social and economic perspective. Research results that meet a real market need may provide competitive advantages with respect to existing alternatives, thus making them good candidates for commercialization.

Within this context, D4.6 “Boosting Commercialisation potential of research results”, as part of WP4, aims to design and deliver a two-day bootcamp within the ENoLL Annual Conference “Open Living Lab Days” for building-up entrepreneurial skills and capacities with a roadmap on how to transform knowledge into impactful solutions of high commercialisation potential.

The VITALISE project grants free Transnational Access to external researchers from multiple disciplines to the project’s Living Lab Research Infrastructures. The external researchers approved for Transnational Access will have the opportunity to conduct research studies in the available infrastructures and be granted Virtual Access to datasets collected during the Joint Research Activities of the project for further analysis. The provision of Transnational Access will be implemented through three (3) Open Calls that will be conducted in: (i) March 2022, (ii) December 2022 and (iii) May 2023.

The bootcamp will empower Transnational Access researchers to advance themselves, their team and their organisations and accelerate their efforts to reach the market. The acceleration bootcamp is built upon the Lean Startup Theory¹, and uses practical exercises to assist the participants in developing their business strategy and tactics towards commercialisation. The methodological approach adopted facilitates understanding, reflection, and adaptation.

In addition, this deliverable (D4.8) includes preliminary work on the evaluation framework for assessing the innovation potential of each research conducted during the Transnational and Virtual Access research conducted in VITALISE. To this purpose, the Innovation Radar Methodology² and the Innovation Readiness Level Framework by KTH³ are here adapted to formulate the VITALISE approach for assessing the innovation and commercialisation potential of research results. The purpose of this document is to:

- Present the background of acceleration bootcamps.
- Describe the scope and the content of the VITALISE bootcamp and outline rules for team selection and time schedule for the two-day bootcamps to be delivered during the project.
- Introduce a preliminary evaluation framework for assessing the innovation and commercialisation potential of research conducted during TAs and VAs
- Outline the VITALISE approach for assessing innovation potential.

The bootcamp will be implemented after the First VITALISE Summer School which will be held in Greece (Marathon) in July 2022, and in parallel with the Open Living Lab Days 2022 taking place from 21 to 23 September 2022 in Turin, Italy. It will also be repeated in 2023 in parallel with the second Summer School (the exact date to be decided within the consortium). The complete framework for evaluating the innovation and commercialisation potential is presented in Task 13.3 (more details are provided in §1.3). D4.8 includes only the background research on relevant evaluation frameworks and some preliminary proposals for adapting existing frameworks.

¹ <http://theleanstartup.com/principles>

² Innovation Radar: Identifying Innovations and Innovators with High Potential in ICT FP7, CIP & H2020 Projects. JRC SCIENCE AND POLICY REPORT, 2015. Accessed online on 13.03.2022: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC96339/jrc96339.pdf>

³ <https://kthinnovationreadinesslevel.com/>

1. Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need: (i) convenient access to research infrastructures, (ii) direct engagement of people to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and (iii) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g., healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of Health and Wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens Living Lab research infrastructures as the vehicle to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond, by enabling in-person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday living environments through harmonised processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Purpose and scope of Task 4.6 “Boosting Commercialization Potential”

Within the framework of “WP4: NA3-Capacity Building and Training”, “Task 4.6 Boosting Commercialization Potential” led by Anthology Ventures, aims to a) design, and deliver a two-day bootcamp that will increase the researchers’ capacities to exploit their innovative research results i.e., by bringing to market innovative products and services, and b) present a preliminary version of the evaluation framework for assessing the innovation potential of research individuals or teams that have been granted Transnational and Virtual Access (TAs and VAs). During the TAs and VAs researchers from multiple disciplines will be granted access to the physical infrastructures of the project’s Living Lab Research Infrastructures. External researchers will also be granted Virtual Access to datasets collected during the Joint Research Activities of the project for further analysis.

The 2-day acceleration bootcamp will be held during the ENoLL Annual Conference “Open Living Lab Days” (from 21 to 23 September 2022) and will be repeated along with the second Summer School organised by VITALISE (T4.1) in 2023. The bootcamp will combine theoretical content taught through seminars as well as practical work from the participants regarding the commercialisation process. The bootcamp is designed for researchers and professionals who are looking to refine their knowledge and skills on commercialization strategies and apply best practice standards and frameworks for commercialisation. Researchers that have been selected for the VITALISE TA or VA to the Living Lab Research Infrastructures of the project, will be given priority for participating at the bootcamp but it will be generally open to all participants of the ENoLL Annual Conference “Open Living Lab Days”.

The theoretical content will include an introduction to the key principles of entrepreneurship and commercialization that will help all participants understand the process of turning an idea into a business opportunity. Participants will increase their ability to identify monetizable opportunities and plan appropriate paths to market including key elements of business building i.e., gaining a deeper understanding of the need - problem - solution, plan customer validation, understand the competitive landscape, design a financial plan, and prepare for effectively communicating the value of research pitching. The bootcamp will build upon this training and use practical exercises based upon industry-standard Startup Theory and Practices to assist the participants in developing their business strategy

&/or tactics. The bootcamps will employ both daily work and lectures and all participants will be expected to complete tasks/assignments each day. Researchers will pitch to the entire group, and invited members of the local community (academics, business owners) their selected roadmap that will include a desired commercialization outcome. A toolkit of checklists, templates and resources will help guide the success of future commercialization projects.

The toolkit will also include the evaluation framework that can be used for self-assessment guiding idea development and assessing idea status across key dimensions till the project reaches the market. The framework aims to support innovators to understand complex challenges and plan their tactics for creating an impact affecting people's lives. The tool used for assessing the innovation potential of research results will be based on the Innovation Radar Methodology⁴, and the Market Creation Potential Indicator (MCPI)⁵. For the recognized innovations with high potential to reach the market the KTH Innovation Readiness Tool is adapted by AV for the purposes of VITALISE project. The tools and their application are described in detail in Chapter 3, as well as further analysed in D1.6 "Innovation strategy (first version)".

This deliverable also presents the preparatory research conducted about related tools and methodologies for assessing the innovation potential, while the complete evaluation of innovation potential framework will be presented in Task 13.3 "VITALISE Innovation and Commercialization Monitoring System", which is due on M18 (see§1.3).

1.3 Relation to other WPs and tasks

Task 4.6 is directly or indirectly connected with various WPs of the VITALISE project. More specifically T4.6 is directly linked with the WPs focusing on the research conducted during the Transnational Access (TA) activities, as well as via the Virtual Access to datasets (VAs). More specifically:

- **WP8** TA1 – TA to Living Lab infrastructures for rehabilitation.
- **WP9** TA2 – TA to Living Lab infrastructures for transitional care.
- **WP10** TA3 – TA to Living Lab infrastructures for everyday living.
- **WP12** VA1 – Virtual Access (VA) to datasets.

The above WPs include the implementation of research activities performed within the physical infrastructure of the VITALISE Living Labs, and the research activities supported by virtual access to datasets owned by the LLs. In this respect, the research outcomes of the activities conducted in the above work packages will be evaluated in terms of innovation and commercialisation potential with the proposed evaluation framework (see Chapter 3 and D13.3).

Task 4.8 is also directly linked to WP13, and specifically Task 13.3 VITALISE Innovation and Commercialization Monitoring System, which aims to develop the "VITALISE Innovation Monitoring System", a methodology to assess a) innovation potential, b) innovator's capacity, and c) maturity level of innovations. The finalised framework for assessing the innovation and commercialisation potential will be presented in Deliverable 13.3, which is due on M18.

Finally, Task 4.6 is linked with WP1 and specifically with Task 1.6 "Innovation Strategy (first version)", presenting the Innovation Strategy (D1.6) of the VITALISE project. D1.6 includes the evaluation of the innovation and commercialisation potential of the innovations produced during the VITALISE as well as sets the ground for building the VITALISE Innovation Monitoring System. Therefore, the evaluation framework developed in T13.3 will be customised to evaluate two use cases: **a)** research projects conducted during the TAs and VAs, including researchers participating during the bootcamps, and **b)** the VITALISE project research results.

⁴ Innovation Radar: Identifying Innovations and Innovators with High Potential in ICT FP7, CIP & H2020 Projects. JRC SCIENCE AND POLICY REPORT, 2015. Accessed online on 13.03.2022: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC96339/jrc96339.pdf>

⁵ Market Creating Innovations in the EU Framework Programme, JRC Technical Reports, 2020. Accessed online on 13.03.2022: https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC121066/ir_mcpi.pdf

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

This document is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2**, defines the term "bootcamp" and presents an overview of other bootcamp trainings, and their approaches;
- **Chapter 3**, describes the VITALISE approach for the Acceleration Bootcamp, the process of its implementation, the main types of content to be included, and the program outline with expected learning outcomes on the topics to be covered;
- **Chapter 4**, presents the preliminary research conducted for identifying appropriate tools and methods in the literature for monitoring innovation and commercialization potential;
- **Chapter 5**, presents already some adaptations on the existing tools for the purposes of VITALISE project, although the final VITALISE Innovation and Monitoring System will be presented in T13.3 (D13.3);
- **Chapter 6**, describes the coordination process for assessing the innovation potential of the proposed research studies that will be implemented during the provision of TA and VA to the research infrastructures of the project and the initial monitoring action plan;
- **Chapter 7**, describes the exploitation and sustainability plan for the bootcamps and the VITALISE Innovation and Monitoring System offering initial considerations on how to exploit the specific outputs.

A review on Acceleration Bootcamp Training

1.5 Definition of the Term “Bootcamp”

The term “*Bootcamp*” was originally used to describe a type of correctional facility for adolescents, especially in the U.S. penal system or a type of training camp for learning various types of skills or one with military inspired exercises.

Today, the term “bootcamp” is frequently used with its modern adaptations to describe intense learning/training workshops that most often have a duration of a few days or a few weeks maximum. More specifically, within start-up ecosystems, “bootcamps” are implemented globally to enhance the knowledge of start-up teams in various topics, optimise their business model, or focus on a specific topic, like solving a problem with code (i.e., hackathons), reach a milestone or learning how to pitch to investors, etc. Based on their structure and goal, bootcamps were introduced as mini-Startup Accelerators or have evolved to those. Sometimes, startup acceleration programs that last for a few months have borrowed the term “bootcamp” to title to e.g., Startup Bootcamp.

1.6 Indicative Examples that Inspired the VITALISE Acceleration Bootcamps

Indicative examples of other bootcamps were reviewed and several cases combining different initiators or organizers from academia and companies are presented below. The selected bootcamps presented in the rest of this section are mainly from Europe and the US, as they can represent a more suitable fit for better depicting the specific geographical part of the startup ecosystem, that is of interest in the VITALISE context. The bootcamps have both many similarities, as well as differences in their duration, organizers scheme, purpose, as well as focus. More specifically, the bootcamps that were taken into consideration when defining the content of the bootcamps to take place within the framework of the activities of Task 4.6, are the following:

Startup Weekend⁶ is a program run by TechStars, where aspiring entrepreneurs can experience startup life. The program runs in hundreds of cities around the world every year. The event originally implemented by the Kaufman Foundation pioneered the global startup ecosystem with its 54-hour

⁶ <https://www.techstars.com/communities/startup-weekend>

Bootcamps providing an intensive mentoring process based on the Lean Startup Methodology.

The Startup Bootcamp organized by digitalswitzerland⁷ powered by Venturelab, in partnership with Gebert Rűf Stiftung, and Venture Kick brings together industry leaders and established Swiss Accelerator Programmes with leading national and international startups addressing in common their needs for growth.

The INSEAD Startup Bootcamp⁸ is an early-stage program that lasts for a weekend full of training designed to put to the test founders' entrepreneurial appetite and jumpstart their journey. Learning includes a variety of topics including idea generation, team formation, business validation and pitching to investors.

Startup Bootcamp by Columbia University⁹ is a two-week program focused on the Lean Startup methodology and customer validation. A key-element of the program is the interview of at least 20 customers and the confirmation that the solution/technology applied is solving a real-world problem.

The Harvard Business School Startup Bootcamp¹⁰ is an immersion program for first-year MBA candidates applying a "learning-by-doing approach" to help in building skills required as an early-stage entrepreneur. The program allows only for teams of 3 up to 4 persons. To enter the Bootcamp, the applying teams submit a Bootcamp Customer Discovery Deliverable with respective customer interviews validating the assumptions regarding the solution proposed.

Startup Bootcamp by "Founders Illinois"¹¹ is an 8-week lecture series designed to introduce students to the entrepreneurial mindset through interactive workshops, mentors, and other experiences. The Bootcamp, that resembles an early-stage accelerator, integrates a Startup Weekend within the program.

The Startup Clinic of University of Miami School of Law¹² is another type of bootcamp connecting the students with new ventures in need of legal assistance. Attendees of the Startup Clinic help clients with organizing, financing, identify talent, intellectual property, risk, regulation, and other legal issues, as well as with client development and related activities.

Cooperations like EU-Silicon Valley 5-days Entrepreneurship Trainings combine the strengths of different parties like InnMind¹³ and Draper University¹⁴ that offer together a 5-day program through interactive workshops, "know-how" lectures, practical cases, networking opportunities, strategic development techniques. The program sources InnMind's provide access to 10,000+ tech startups from 75+ countries and 2,000 investors from Europe and Draper University's 500+ alumni from 50 countries. The institution helped to build 350+ startups that raised \$470M+ in seed funding from venture investors.

The NVIDIA DOCA Virtual European Hackathon¹⁵ is an example of a more focused and super condensed program that lasts 29 hours. The organisers invite candidates to take part in supercharging their DPU capabilities for AI, networking, storage, and security by familiarizing the participants with the NVIDIA® DOCA™ software framework and building an innovative accelerated application. During the bootcamp, participants build their network, meet NVIDIA experts and learn from them.

The Helmholtz GPU Hackathon¹⁶ is a 4-day bootcamp where Helmholtz Information & Data Science Academy and the AI Campus in Berlin, as well as NVIDIA and OpenACC.org, provide a unique opportunity to all scientists and industry partners to accelerate their AI research and/or HPC codes. Participating Teams get mentorship from academia and industry leaders, and work together in

⁷ <https://digitalswitzerland.com/sub-programm/startup-bootcamp-digitalswitzerland/>

⁸ <https://www.insead.edu/centres/entrepreneurship/startup-bootcamp>

⁹ <https://entrepreneurship.engineering.columbia.edu/bootcamp/>

¹⁰ <http://www.hbsstartupbootcamp.com/>

¹¹ <http://founders.illinois.edu/startupbootcamp/>

¹² <https://www.law.miami.edu/academics/start-up-law-clinic>

¹³ <https://innmind.com/>

¹⁴ <https://www.draperuniversity.com/>

¹⁵ <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/events/doca-hackathon/>

¹⁶ <https://www.gpuhackathons.org/event/helmholtz-gpu-hackathon-2022>

groups of three to six developers to accelerate their own codes on GPUs using a programming model or machine learning framework of their choice.

Table 1 Bootcamp process and Core Elements

	Application	Preparation	Participation
Indicative Objective	Submit application to organizers	Support the bootcamp's objective with relative work to be scrutinized later during the bootcamp	Learn about Entrepreneurship, Write Code, Design Solution-Business Model, How to commercialize product, network, pitch
Duration	Few weeks to a few months		From 24 hours to a few months
Indicative Outcome	Application submission for approval to enter bootcamp	Prepare and submit accompanying material or perform certain pre-bootcamp work	Understanding of commercialization and funding mechanics, network with like-minded persons and ecosystem stakeholders, access to Proof Of Concept (PoC) /test-bed capabilities

1.7 Strategic Focus of the VITALISE Acceleration Bootcamps

In a similar situation to bootcamps, NESTA¹⁷ has created segmented Accelerators based on their **strategic focus** in four categories that are adopted for the purposes of VITALISE bootcamps:

- **Investor/Organizer Led:** the investor-led programs receive funding from investors such as business angels, venture capital funds or corporate venture capital. The objective is to bridge the equity gap between very early-stage projects and investment ready businesses.
- **Match-maker:** is usually set up by companies who providing services to their own customers or stakeholders. In this respect, the organizer may offer its establishment as a test bed to collaborate on innovation with early-stage ventures – and in the process, strengthen its relationship with its clients or stakeholders.
- **Ecosystem Builder:** these programs typically have government agencies as a main stakeholder, but they can also be implemented by private institutions or a mix of them in consortia. Organizers are interested in stimulating startup activity, either within a specific region or within a specific technological domain. For instance, the European Commission stimulates the establishment of accelerators within the major technological programs (Knowledge and Innovation Communities or KICs), which it finances.
- **Hybrids:** hybrid programs are combining elements found in bootcamp programs with a focus on supporting startups and building the ecosystem but also addressing the investment readiness aspects typically found in the investor-related types of bootcamps. Consequently, the objective of these programs is also hybrid.

The VITALISE Bootcamp (see detailed analysis in Section 3), is a hybrid program combining elements that **a)** aim to strengthen the startup ecosystem stemming from the consortium's efforts to stimulate commercialization of research results produced in the framework of the Living Labs, but it also **b)** contains "Match-Maker" elements from the perspective of offering access to the Living Labs infrastructure along with a variety of services i.e. networking, end users engagement in the validation process etc.

The VITALISE Project Acceleration Bootcamp

¹⁷ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/>

This section outlines the VITALISE approach for the Acceleration bootcamp and presents the context the scope as well as its learning outcomes.

1.8 Bootcamp Outline

Two acceleration bootcamps with a duration of two days each will be implemented within VITALISE. The first one will be conducted following the Summer School implemented in July 2022 in Athens, and in parallel with the Annual Conference “Open Living Lab Days” 2022 organized by the European Network of Living Labs in September 2022 in Turin (Italy). The aim of making a joint effort of the VITALISE first bootcamp with OLLD 2022 is to reach out to a high number of researchers, also to the ones selected to participate in the Transnational Access Research activities of VITALISE. The second bootcamp will be implemented in parallel to the second VITALISE Summer School in 2023.

The VITALISE bootcamp will combine theoretical content, as well as practical work for the participants. Bootcamp applicants that have been selected to conduct research in the context of TAs or VAs will be given a priority for attending the bootcamp. Virtual Access research projects supported by the VITALISE LLs will commence with the launch of the second Open Call (2023). All researchers selected to participate in the TAs or VAs will be invited to participate to the bootcamps.

The VITALISE bootcamps will introduce key principles of entrepreneurship from developing an idea into a business concept, to confirming the assumptions regarding need/problem/solution with customer validation, analysis of the competitive landscape, project finances and pitching. The bootcamp will adapt standard practices of the Lean Startup Methodology¹⁸ to assist the participants in developing their business strategy and/or tactics. Topics to be covered are:

- Commercialisation Principles (from Research to the Market).
- Estimating and relating Market Size to Customer Need and Readiness.
- Competition Analysis.
- Investment Basics and Attraction of Investment.
- Business Model, Team and Incorporation.
- Pitching.

The bootcamps will combine lectures with daily work, and all participants will be expected to complete tasks/assignments within each day. On the final day of each bootcamp (second day) the researchers will pitch to the entire group, and invited members of the local community (academics, business owners). The bootcamp content will adopt the “Understand – Reflect – Adapt” principles (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Understand – Reflect – Adapt Principles adopted by VITALISE.

Table 2 presents the bootcamp scenario to be implemented during the VITALISE project. The

¹⁸ <http://theleanstartup.com/>

scenario includes three phases: a) the *application phase* where a marketing campaign designed with the support of VILABS and ENOLL will be promoted to attract interested researchers, b) the *preparation phase*, where selected participants will be introduced to the general concepts of commercialisation, and c) the *participation phase*, where the actual 2-day acceleration bootcamp will be realised.

Table 2 Analysis of Bootcamp Scenario

Bootcamp Objective	
Application (Phase 1)	During the bootcamp application phase interested researcher will be asked to complete a self- assessment tool depicting the maturity level of their research projects in terms of innovation potential. The self-assessment tool will be an adaptation of the VITALISE Innovation Monitoring System (D13.3) i.e., a shorter online version of the monitoring system. This initial innovation potential profile of the research projects will be used to assess the maturity of the projects participating in the bootcamp and inform the bootcamp content material (if necessary) to suit the needs of the attendees depending on their current maturity stage.
Preparation (Phase 2)	An introduction to the bootcamp training material will be sent to all selected attendees to introduce the researchers to the bootcamp's philosophy on Commercialisation.
Participation (Phase 3)	The third includes the actual 2-day bootcamp event aiming to increase understanding of commercialisation strategies, tactics and funding mechanics and be able to present a Commercialisation Roadmap draft.
Duration	
Application (Phase 1)	1 month (starting: Bootcamp Day – 2 months i.e., July 2022)
Preparation (Phase 2)	1 month (starting: Bootcamp Day – 1 month, i.e., August 2022)
Participation (Phase 3)	2 Days (21-23 September 2022)
Process/ Outcome	
Application (Phase 1)	<p>Researchers selected to participate to VITALISE TAs or VAs, will be given priority over their acceptance to the bootcamp.</p> <p>Researchers applying either as a team or individually will conduct an exercise of depicting the current status of innovation and commercialisation potential by submitting their self – assessment report using the tool provided during the application phase.</p>
Preparation (Phase 2)	<p>In order for the researchers to effectively attend the bootcamp, a set of training material with the bootcamp agenda and relative theoretical content and tools will be provided ahead of the start of the event. This will offer the opportunity to attendees to familiarise themselves with some general business development concepts and the basics on commercialisation.</p> <p>The assessment will be discussed and re-evaluated at the end of the bootcamp.</p>
Participation (Phase 3)	During the Bootcamp, the selected researchers will attend a rigorous mix of seminars and workshops complementing back-to-back each-other and providing the basis for understanding commercialisation practices. During the workshops, critical elements of commercialisation practices will be introduced

	leading the researchers to their conclusive pitch using a commercialisation deck especially developed for the needs of the VITALISE project.
--	--

1.9 Research Team Selection

Research Teams will apply online for the bootcamp and up to seventeen teams of one to four researchers each, will be selected to participate. The applicants will be evaluated following specific eligibility criteria. The selected teams will be able to proceed to the evaluation phase. All applications will be reviewed based on 5 dimensions: Team, Sustainability, Market, Product, Innovation according to the following evaluation criteria:

Table 3 Bootcamp Teams selection criteria

	<i>1 point</i>	<i>2 points</i>	<i>3 points</i>
Team	1-person “team” or non-interdisciplinary team	Interdisciplinary team 2-3 persons	Female in leading roles (but not a 1-person “team”)
Concept Condition	Concept exists as an idea	Concept with structure	Validated concept
Market	Local Market focus	Regional Market focus	Global market focus
Product	Pre-prototype basic	Prototype status created for a specific market	Pre-Commercial Prototype beta tested Developed and tested
Innovation	Straight forward but nothing exotic	Has a reasonable innovation potential locally/regionally	Innovation potential combined with Intellectual Property Certificates
Participation in the TAs/VAs	No	Yes	-

A promising mix of teams will be finally selected. Relevant factors for the selection will be gender balance, diversity and multidisciplinary teams. Research Teams selected for TAs/VAs will be given a bonus point.

1.10 Research Teams co-pilot mentors

Each researcher or team participating in the bootcamps will be matched with one mentor called “Team Co-Pilot” (TCP) that will support the team during the whole bootcamp program. The TCP will guide the researchers by reflecting on the bootcamp training materials and adapting the introduced theory and principles to their own project to design forward steps.

1.11 Time schedule and training material

The VITALISE bootcamp timetable and schedule is designed and presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4. Time SCHEDULE of the VITALISE Bootcamp

Time/Duration		Activity	Content/Details
D* -60 days		Online Application	AV, VILABS, ENOLL with the support of other partners promote the bootcamp to relevant audiences
D* -30 days		Sent Bootcamp Package	Attendees receive via email: General Agenda and Travel Pack, Training Content and the Rules of Engagement
D -15 days		Process of Assessments	Preliminary Statistics are prepared for a) the participants of the bootcamp, and b) each individual project/team
Bootcamp Day 1			
09:00	09:15	Get coffee	Get ready
09:15	10:00	Presentation - Q &A's	Introduction to Vitalise Bootcamp 2022 and the rules of engagement
10:00	10:45	Guest Speaker	The pathway to Commercialization (Guest Speaker)
10:45	11:30	Lecture	Assesment of Commercialization Pottential: The Vitalise Approach (CRL, TRL, BRL, IPRL, TMRL, SRL, LRL, FRL + IR / MCPI)
11:30	11:45	Break	
11:45	13:15	Workshop	Presentation of Preliminary Statitics. Discussion on initial impressions and potential problems with Commercialization
13:15	14:30	Workshop	Analysing Customer Need / Readiness; Mapping Competition, Defining Market Size
14:30	15:30	Break	
15:30	17:00	Workshop	a) Presentations of Attendees of findings regarding Market Size, Need and Competition and Feedback Session b) How to make a first, fast version of your Deck
17:00	17:30	Instructions for next day	Attendees receive instructions on what the next day will include and what to prepare
Bootcamp Day 2			
09:00	09:15	Get coffee	Get ready
09:15	10:00	Lecture	Investment Basics for Tech Startups: Funding Cycles & Structures
10:00	10:45	Lecture	Selection of the Appropriate Pathway for Commercialization (Business Model, Legal Form, Key partners, Team, ...)
10:45	11:30	Workshop	Work on Business Model and Selection of the Appropriate Pathway for Commercialization (with related resources)
11:30	11:45	Break	
11:45	14:30	Workshop	Preparation of "Commercialization Potential" Decks
14:30	15:30	Break	
15:30	17:00	Presentation - Q &A's	Final Pitching: Presentations of Attendees of findings regarding the Commercialization Potential of their Project (Evaluated using Vitalise Framework)

*D – Bootcamp Date

A training material pack for the sessions described in the time schedule has been developed and uploaded to the project's online folder in Teams¹⁹ and a shared Google Drive folder²⁰. The material will be subject to refinements and updates upon the date of the bootcamp delivery and the final version of the material will be submitted along with the rest of the training material that will be developed for the Summer School in T4.2 and T4.3.

Monitoring Innovation and Commercialisation Potential: Literature review and Overview of Relevant Tools

There are two separate use cases for evaluating the innovative and commercialisation potential of research results in the context of the VITALISE project. The first use case concerns the assessment of results obtained from the research teams, which will utilise the Living Labs' infrastructure in response to the project's Open Calls during the TAs and VAs (D11.2). The second use case involves the assessment of the VITALISE results, which concerns the deliverables produced by the consortium partners during the project (D13.3). Thus, a framework that can be customised accordingly for the two use cases will be developed. An initial elaboration is presented in D1.6 "Innovation strategy (first version), and on the chapters to follow.

We hereby present preliminary work conducted towards designing the VITALISE Innovation Monitoring System. We rely on three different models of assessment frameworks: **a)** the process-based European Union's Innovation Radar, **b)** the Market Creation Potential Indicator, which is based on the Innovation Radar Methodology, and **c)** the more culture-oriented Innovation Readiness Level developed by the KTH Royal Institute of Technology Stockholm as the baseline mechanisms. Those tools will be adapted and used complementarily to accommodate the specific needs of the VITALISE project and in specific the two used cases described above. The next chapter includes a brief overview of these methodologies.

1.12 Innovation Radar Framework Background

The Innovation Radar Methodology is a framework applied to projects funded through European Union programmes, such as FP7 and Horizon 2020. Initially launched in May 2014, in the context of evaluating FP7 ICT projects, the Innovation Radar (IR) aims to identify high-potential innovations and innovators. It is an important source of actionable intelligence on innovations emerging from research and innovation projects and has been used throughout the Horizon 2020 programme. The Innovation Radar framework consists of a survey (i.e., the Innovation Radar Survey, IRS) which is administered by an independent reviewer at three points in time during a project's lifecycle. The IRS results serve to identify exploitable innovations in the project and up to three key organizations fostering this exploitation.

In addition to the survey assessment framework, the Innovation Radar serves as a source for dissemination and discovery of innovative products and technologies via an online platform i.e., the Innovation Radar Portal²¹. The portal provides summaries of EU-funded innovations in various stages of commercialisation, providing a searching engine²² in terms of i.e., geographic, technology-type, women-led, SDG-orientation, etc. for locating companies that have received funding from EU programmes. There is also an IR Prize competition for companies whose technology has been assessed using the IR methodology, and a platform area²³ that offers services for companies who are seeking financing to further advance their development (this is maintained in partnership with dealroom.eu). The evolution of this portal reflects a deeper understanding of the technology transfer and commercialisation process that has been facilitated by the inclusion and employment of the Market Creation Potential Indicator -MCPI (discussed in the next section).

1.12.1 Innovation Radar Survey

¹⁹ [https://aristotleuniversity.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/VITALISE-](https://aristotleuniversity.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/VITALISE-H20202/Shared%20Documents/WP4%20(ENoLL)/T4.6%20BOOSTING%20COMMERCIALISATION?csf=1&web=1&e=Yd4ICi)

[H20202/Shared%20Documents/WP4%20\(ENoLL\)/T4.6%20BOOSTING%20COMMERCIALISATION?csf=1&web=1&e=Yd4ICi](https://aristotleuniversity.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/VITALISE-H20202/Shared%20Documents/WP4%20(ENoLL)/T4.6%20BOOSTING%20COMMERCIALISATION?csf=1&web=1&e=Yd4ICi)

²⁰ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1K89rPyxrlUm91ppzbh1eUeJKRAoKb9X6?usp=sharing>

²¹ <https://www.innoradar.eu/>

²² <https://www.innoradar.eu/spotlight>

²³ <https://www.innoradar.eu/dealfow>

The IRS is a process-based tool, utilizing pre-defined questions that are scored in a weighted process to produce an overall score indicating the commercialisation potential of the innovation (see Annex A). Its main elements involve assessing, guiding, and supporting the transition of highly innovative research results from the laboratory into the market.

Data underpinning the Innovation Radar stem from a survey developed by the Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (CONNECT) and the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission. According to a summary report ²⁴, the methodology is intended to provide “up-to-date intelligence on the innovative output of EU-funded research projects and guidance on how to leverage the innovative output of the ICT FP7/CIP projects.” It was also suggested to be used “for monitoring the progress of innovations and innovators and for assessing the effectiveness of policy for innovations and innovators (which) could be extended to the entire FP7 and, at a later stage, to the H2020 programme.”

The tool uses two composite indicators (**the Innovation Potential Indicator** or **IPI**, and the **Innovator’s Capacity Indicator** or **ICI**) to assess two components of an innovation: the innovation *potential* and the innovators’ *capacity*. The Innovation Potential aims to measure the development towards commercialisation, while the Innovators’ Capacity aims to capture the innovative capacity of the organizations behind these innovations.

Figure 2. The Innovation Potential Indicator and Innovator’s Capacity Indicator of the Innovation Radar Methodology

(Source: Innovation Radar: Identifying Innovations and Innovators with High Potential in ICT FP7, CIP & H2020 Projects. JRC SCIENCE AND POLICY REPORT, 2015.)

1.12.2 Innovation Potential Indicator

The **Innovation Potential Indicator** encompasses three indicators that capture essential steps in the innovation development process:

- **Innovation Readiness:**

This indicator relates to the technical maturity of evolving innovations. It aims to define the development phase of innovations. It accounts for the steps undertaken to prepare them for commercialisation (e.g., prototyping, demonstration or testing activities or a feasibility study) and to secure their technological resources. Furthermore, this indicator considers the time to the potential commercialisation.

- **Innovation management:**

²⁴ Innovation Radar: Identifying Innovations and Innovators with High Potential in ICT FP7, CIP & H2020 Projects. JRC SCIENCE AND POLICY REPORT, 2015. Accessed online on 13.03.2022: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC96339/jrc96339.pdf>

This indicator addresses the project consortium and its commitment to bring innovations to the market. It aims to measure the capability of management teams to transform novel technologies or research results into marketable products or services. To this purpose, this indicator includes, among others, clarifying the related ownership and IPR issues, preparing a business plan or market study, securing capital investment from public and private sources, or engaging potential end-users in the project.

- **Market potential:**

This indicator relates to the demand and supply side of innovations. Regarding the demand side, it concerns the prospective market conditions and the chances of successful commercialisation. It aims to assess how products or services satisfy a market sector and serve a potential customer base. With respect to the supply side, it aims to assess whether there are potential barriers (e.g., regulatory frameworks or existing IPR issues) which could weaken the commercial exploitation of innovations.

The **Innovation Potential Indicator** is created as an arithmetic aggregate of these three indicators.

1.12.3 Innovator Capacity Indicator

The Innovator Capacity Indicator encompasses two indicators that capture the capacity of innovators in conducting and delivering successful innovations:

- **Innovator's ability:**

This indicator relates to the ability of organisations in developing innovations within the EC-funded activities. It accounts for the number of times organisations have been identified by the Innovation Radar as key innovators. It includes other factors such as reviewers' opinions about innovators' potential and independence in fulfilling the market potential of innovations.

- **Innovator's environment:**

This indicator aims to capture the overall conditions in the project consortium which an innovator face. It relates to the composition and activity of partner organisations, the performance of the project in terms of innovations, and the commitment of relevant partners to exploiting innovations. Moreover, it also considers the presence of organisations that are directly interested in exploiting the innovations. It is assumed that a positive environment will have positive knowledge spillovers between innovators and their environments.

The **Innovator Capacity Indicator** is created as an arithmetic aggregate of these two indicators.

1.13 The Market Creation Potential Indicator - MCPI

There is a great deal of literature on the role of public funding in market creation and disruption²⁸. Traditionally, lower, and less socially optimal investments in R&I, and the insufficient supply of capital for high-risk investments²⁵ have driven the need for enhanced public support to compensate for that requirement. Public policy does not only appropriate markets, but often it can create them^{26,27} where private funding is inadequate or a remote chance for innovators.

At the time that the Innovation Radar was launched (2014), it was engineered to leverage the outcomes of public money spent on research by offering intelligence that could be deployed to help

²⁵ Martin, S., & Scott, J. (2000). The nature of innovation market failure and the design of public support for private innovation. *Research Policy*, 29(4), 437-447.

²⁶ Mazzucato, M. (2016). From market fixing to market-creating: a new framework for innovation policy. *Industry and Innovation*, 23(2), 140-156. doi: 10.1080/13662716.2016.1146124.

²⁷ NIST. (2019). Return on Investment Initiative for Unleashing American Innovation NIST Special Publication 1234: National Institute of Standards and Technology.

EU-funded research projects with cutting-edge technologies find their way into the market. Yet while the survey makes use of composite indicators to capture the complexity of innovation development and commercialisation process, and profiles the innovators behind these innovations, it does not address the issue of “disruptive innovation”. In other words, *if* and *how* the commercialised product may either enter an already established market, or preferably create a market. Thus, the Market Creation Potential Indicator was added to the assessment process as a means to understand where the innovation might fit and what degree of commercial impact it could possibly achieve. The MCPI provided a new “toolset to measure and assess the market-creating effect of public R&I policies.” (From the report: [Market Creating Innovations in the EU Framework Programme²⁸](#)) The toolset presented provides a new benchmark to assess an innovation's potential to expand the market scope.

There are two main concepts of market creating innovations by which we can understand MCPI:

- **“Disruptive Innovation”²⁹**, whereby an innovation offers previously expensive or high-end products or services to new customers under a more affordable and accessible marketing mix, thus reaching a broader population that was previously excluded from the market. A newcomer introduces a Disruptive innovation into a market niche that incumbent firms do not serve. The new product is typically of inferior quality and the challenger offers it at a lower price compared to the existing products. By attracting a group of customers that were previously excluded from the market, **the Disruptive innovation extends the market scope.**
- **“Blue Ocean Innovation”^{30,31}**, whereby an innovation addresses the simultaneous pursuits of differentiation and low cost to open a new market space and create new demand by attacking an uncontested market space of an unknown industry or innovation. In contrast to a disruptive innovation, a Blue Ocean innovation does not displace an existing product. Rather than targeting customers who accept inferior quality, it combines features that were not present before. This way, **the Blue Ocean innovation creates new demand and defines a new market.**

Building on the notions of disruptive and blue ocean innovation, the current methodology assumes that for an innovation to have a Market Creation Potential it has to fulfil three conditions:

- the market targeted by this innovation is emerging or not yet existing, but there are chances that an innovation can create it.
- organizations developing such innovations need to have plans to exploit them commercially.
- they need to target new customers.

Innovations identified by the Innovation Radar that fulfil these conditions are subsequently assessed with respect to the level of their Market Creation Potential. As shown in the table below, the questions begin with the market maturity, rather than the innovation status, and attempt to rate the possibility for market disruption or creation. Table 5, presents the decision rules used to determine the level of Market Creation Potential of innovation identified by the Innovation Radar. The framework is based on the Innovation Radar Survey.

Table 5 Market Creation Potential Indicator Decision Rules

What is the maturity of the market targeted by the	How will the innovation be exploited?	Who will use the innovation?	What is the level of innovation?	What is the type of innovation?	Market Creation Potential Level
--	---------------------------------------	------------------------------	----------------------------------	---------------------------------	---------------------------------

²⁸ Market Creating Innovations in the EU Framework Programme, JRC Technical Reports, 2020. Accessed online on 13.03.2022: https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC121066/ir_mcpi.pdf

²⁹ Christensen, C. (1997). The Innovator's Dilemma: When New Technologies Cause Great Firms to Fail. Cambridge: Harvard Business Review Press.

³⁰ Kim, W., & Mauborgne, R. (1999). Creating New Market Space. Harvard Business Review(January-February).

³¹ Kim, W., & Mauborgne, R. (2004). Blue Ocean Strategy. Harvard Business Review(October).

innovation?					
Emerging or there are chances that an innovation can create it.	The innovation will be introduced as new to the market	New customers	Very Innovative	New product, process or service	(5) Very high
				Significantly improved product, process or service	(4) High
			Obviously innovative and easily appreciated advantages to customer	New product, process or service	(3) Noteworthy
				Significantly improved product, process or service	
			Innovative but could be difficult to convert customers	New product, process or service	
				Significantly improved product, process or service	(2) Moderate
			Minor improvements over existing products	New or significantly improved	(1) Minor

Source: DG CNECT and DG JRC

One of the main benefits of the MCPI is recognizing and recording the contribution of the public sector as a “lead investor” that provides funding to high-risk projects, and as such, acknowledge the contribution of public support to creating new markets. After comparing 6352 innovations (identified by the Innovation Radar Survey) across 1704 FP projects within the period January 2016 and March 2020, research found that 35% included innovations that were either creating a market or extending the market scope while 14% had a high or very high Market Creation Potential. In addition, 47% of all innovations that showed some Market Creation Potential included contributions from SMEs. These findings highlight that “key” role that SMEs play in delivering innovations to the market³², and that their share of innovations with market potential is significantly higher than the average. This illustrates the importance of SME’s in “Disruption,” which by nature is a process whereby a smaller company with fewer resources can successfully challenge established, larger businesses. The IR/MCPI conclusions support the value that SMEs can bring to a consortium, carrying as it were the genome of a player with the potential to do more with less resources, as well as more successfully

³² De Prato, G., Nepelski, D., & Piroli, G. (2015a). Innovation Radar: Identifying Innovations and Innovators with High Potential in ICT FP7, CIP & H2020 Projects. Seville: JRC.

identifying needs and targeting potential customers in overlooked segments.

An innovator has a choice between introducing a product that will compete with existing offerings or address an unserved market niche³³. MCPI employs a set of decision rules which attempt to identify if and how the innovation will be used in a new market or be used by a new set of early adopters. The MCPI framework allows to a) classify the type of Innovation and b) the Market Creation Potential Level. Depending on the sequence of criteria, an innovation is ranked with one out of five Market Creation Potential levels ranging from one (minor) to five (very high).

Another finding on Market Creation Potential that carries some statistical value is that Market Creation Potential depends on the technological domain. For example, innovations in eHealth or medical diagnostics have, on average, higher MCPI scores. As mentioned above, the MCPI report attempts to assess the nature of Market Creation Potential of innovations from publicly funded research projects. The report claims it is a novel way for stakeholders in the public and private spheres to navigate the outputs of the EU's Framework Programme and identify the opportunities it presents to create new markets. Finally, the Market Creation Potential Indicator (MCPI) suggests that innovations' ability to capitalize on market potential can be compromised by a relative lack of commercial exploitation plans.

1.14 The KTH Innovation Readiness Level

The KTH Innovation Readiness Level™ Model³⁴ is a tool for assessing innovation projects in terms of customer readiness (CR), Technology Readiness (TR), Business Readiness (BR), IPR Readiness (IPR), Team Readiness (TMR) and Funding Readiness (FR). The tool allows the monitoring of the current development status of a business concept, and the planning of appropriate next steps towards increasing the maturity of a business concept. The model focuses to early stages and technology-based ideas, and due to its generic format, it is applicable to various technological sectors independent of the business concept. Specifically, the models' six key areas of innovation development are:

- **Customer Readiness Level (CRL)**, confirming the customer need and interest.
- **Technology Readiness Level (TRL)**, assessing the stage of development and testing of the technology, product, service, or concept.
- **Business Readiness Level (BRL)**, assessing whether the concept can be financially viable and feasible.
- **IPR Readiness Level (IPRL)**, clarifying the legal and IP situation and secure relevant IP protection.
- **Team Readiness Level (TMRL)**, assessing the right competencies and alignment of the team.
- **Funding Readiness Level (FRL)**, assessing the identification of the necessary funding to take the idea to the market.

The assessment outcome of each innovation project is depicted on a spider graph (see Figure 3) and presents the result of the scores obtained for the six areas of innovation development (a-f).

³³ Abernathy, W., & Clark, K. (1985). Innovation: Mapping the winds of creative destruction. *Research Policy*, 14(1), 3-22.

³⁴ <https://kthinnovationreadinesslevel.com/about/>

Figure 3. The KTH Innovation Readiness Level³⁵

Within each of the six areas, readiness levels ranging from RL one to nine are described with clear definitions of criteria, milestones, and activities for each level. In the scale from one to nine, one means that there is a very early-stage idea or a research result that seems interesting, and nine means the innovation is fully functioning and implemented on the market. The 1-9 scale of maturity was initially brought by NASA to assess the technology readiness of technological contexts and develop Technology Maturity Plans³⁶. The approach was adopted by the European Commission to reflect on the technological maturity levels of Key Enabling Technologies (KET), which have become the backbone of current EU funding evaluation system of Research, Development and Innovation. The KTH tool as a maturity assessment framework helps in guiding on the next to be followed depending on the current status but provides an idea of the overall achievements to be pursued for reaching the commercialization stage and the market. However, the scope of the tools is not to measure how good the idea is but mainly if the right progress towards commercialization is achieved.

The KTH IRL tool is based on the KTH innovation process, which prioritizes ideas based on quantifiable levels of maturity. The KTH innovation process (Figure 2) includes four steps of maturity. The first step is about the “Initial Contact”, which includes the identification of the initial idea and checks some basic factors i.e., ownership. The next phase includes the “Idea phase”, which is about describing the potential of a business idea and checks the idea owners’ drive and planning. The third phase is the “Pre-study” phase, which is a validation phase and verifies key areas such as: (a) Customer, (b) Technology, (c) Business, (d) IPR, (e) Team, and (f) Funding. In order to advance to the next phase, which is the “Project” phase, certain milestones need to be reached i.e., score above the threshold of four (RL>4) in all six areas. The “Project phase” focuses more on the commercial development i.e., establishing customer relationships or conducting pilots (CRL), conducting field or user tests of more advanced prototypes (TRL), define and test a business model, including a revenue model (BRL), secure and develop complementing forms of IPR according to the adapted strategy (IPRL), continue to build the team and include other entrepreneurs (TMRL), prepare pitching materials for securing funding (FRL).

³⁵ <https://kthinnovationreadinesslevel.com/>

³⁶ United States Department of Energy. 2009. Technology Readiness Assessment Guide, Washington, DC 20585. Retrieved March 2022 from <https://www.directives.doe.gov/directives-documents/400-series/0413.3-EGuide-04>

Figure 4 The KTH Innovation Readiness Level Process

The above model has already been used in a wide range of cases at the Royal Institute of Technology Stockholm (KTH) with great results supporting idea owners as well as coaches and advisors through the early stages of developing but also verifying innovative ideas. The model can be also highly useful tool for teams developing ideas and coaches or managers supporting idea development to measure progress and status. The model is supplied via access to an online resource library where all descriptions and documents can be found. The definitions of criteria, milestones and activities for each level are presented in the Annex. The KTH tool is under a Creative Common's license.

1.15 Other Start up Assessment Tools

A search on other tools attempting to measure the innovation or commercialisation potential of new technologies in different context i.e., assessing investment readiness, validate the potential of startups, promote commercialisation of research conducted in university partnerships, high growth is presented below.

- **ABACA:** A tool designed by Village Capital that makes an assessment of investment readiness for startups and then matches with investors. Abaca³⁷ provides results with a benchmarking process in different areas by creating a 9-level, grid ranking 8 categories i.e., problem, need, validation, product, market, business model, strategy³⁸. The framework is called VIRAL (Venture Investment Readiness Assessment Levels) and is used by Maine Technology Institute³⁹.
- **FVR:** A tool for validating a startup's potential to emerge as a winning technology/product in the industrial digital transformation market. The primary objective of this tool is to reveal high-growth industrial technology companies^{40,41}.
- **TEDCO:** TEDCO and The Maryland Innovation Initiative (MII), a partnership between the State of Maryland and five Maryland academic research institutions (Johns Hopkins University; Morgan State University; University of Maryland, Baltimore; University of Maryland, Baltimore County; University of Maryland, College Park) all aiming to promote commercialization of research conducted in the partnership universities and leverage each institution's strengths have designed an on-line tool to make a preliminary assessment⁴².
- **KEY2INVESTORS:** Investment Readiness Check is a tool partly funded by The Austrian

³⁷ <https://abaca.app/>

³⁸ <https://medium.datadriveninvestor.com/the-investment-readiness-tool-that-helped-startups-raise-500m-in-additional-capital-bb625a38a31a>.

³⁹ <https://www.mainetechnology.org/partners-resources/viral/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.forgeforward.in/resources/fvr>

⁴¹ <https://blog.forgeforward.in/forge-venture-rubric-a-startup-diagnostic-tool-b7b840efe337>

⁴² <https://www.tedcmd.com/assessment-tool>

Federal State and FFG within the program AT:net⁴³. The Austrian Development Agency⁴⁴, the operational unit of Austrian Development Cooperation, to support expansion to the African continent together with 3rd parties^{45,46}.

- **STARTUP READINESS ASSESSMENT:** Driven by Artificial Intelligence data over 200,000 global startup Investments over 40 risk parameters; the tool developed by ALCOR fund is aiming in helping founders do a preliminary assessment⁴⁷.

It is worth mentioning that there are several other tools have been developed for offering guidance on conducting due diligence for startups⁴⁸, validating technologies in real life environments⁴⁹, providing self-diagnostics techniques for new technology-based small firms helping investors decide on whether to invest in a new company⁵⁰ and act as central hubs for addressing commercialization challenges with customized dashboards for managing data and produce reports⁵¹.

VITALISE Assessment Framework on the Innovation Potential of Research Teams in TA /VA

The assessment of Innovation Potential, as well as of Market Creation Potential, that both the IR and MCPI were designed for, partially cover the different aspects of commercialisation needs. This stems from their 'process-based' frameworks i.e., different parameters that explore the top-level status of exploitation (Q6, Q7 or Q13, for instance, see Annex A), do not provide the details necessary to assess real issues related to commercialization. However, such information is vital to the diligence process applied by a business angel or an institutional investing entity when examining a case for funding.

This is also related to the underlying premise of the IR/MCPI, i.e., establishing the social and commercial value of public funding. While justifiably appreciating the role of public finance, the frameworks arguably miss several crucial types of information that would be used as investment criteria by private funding sources.

The past several years has seen a substantial increase in Venture Capital funding that supports commercialization of publicly developed innovation. This is true of fully private VC firms as well as hybrid VC Funds where public entities (the EIF being the primary player) participate as limited partners, sometimes contributing as much as 90% of the total capital under management in a select fund. These funds are typically managed with the same practices as their private counterparts and expected to perform with industry-standard rates of return. As such, candidates for investment are evaluated based upon common standards and criteria that employ both procedural and cultural approaches. These assessment methods have evolved to combine quantitative frameworks with experiential and market data, often enhanced with AI, producing software tools that have themselves become commercial items via SaaS and PaaS models.

For the purposes of the VITALISE project, a hybrid framework which combines the process-based quantified approach of the IR/MCPI focusing on how public finding fosters the creation of exploitable innovations along with evaluation criteria of a more culturally based tool i.e., the KTH Innovation Readiness Level, used for the diligence process of private funding decision on innovative products will be adopted for evaluating the commercialization potential of associated innovations and project's results. The final methodology of the VITALSIE Innovation Monitoring System will be presented in D13.3.

⁴³ https://www.ffg.at/atnet_markteinfuehrung

⁴⁴ <https://www.entwicklung.at/>

⁴⁵ <https://key2investors.com/tools/investor-readiness-check/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.konsultori.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/20211020-Press-release-konsultori-Key2Investors-Investor-Readiness-Check-online-Tool-for-Self-Assessment-final.pdf>

⁴⁷ <https://alcorfund.com/do-startup-readiness-assessment/>

⁴⁸ <https://www.lapiana.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/Tool-for-Assessing-Startup-Organizations.pdf>

⁴⁹ <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/77246>

⁵⁰ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280832745_Tech_Transfer_Section_The_Klofsten_Business_Platform_as_a_self-diagnostic_tool_for_new_technology-based_small_firms

⁵¹ <https://cayuse.com/inventions/>

Regarding the KTH Innovation Readiness framework, it is envisaged to be adapted to include further parameters specific to our project’s needs. For example, the informative value of using Customer Readiness (CR), Technology Readiness (TR), Business Readiness (BR), IPR Readiness (IPR), Team Readiness (TMR) and Funding Readiness (FR) within a commercialization potential assessment exercise might be profitably extended by the consideration of two more related dimensions of maturity models⁵² – namely:

- The integration of **societal aspects** in technology modelling and experimentation, with a focus on the readiness to adopt the resulting innovation, measured by a 9-stage SRL (Societal Readiness Level) scale.
- The complex interaction with the **legal and ethical** (values) system, including any pressure to modify it because of the new innovative solution, measured by a 9-stage LRL (Legal Readiness Level) scale.

The resulting proposed 8-dimension Innovation Readiness framework is based on the extension and generalization of the KTH tool in two further directions, namely the Societal and Legal Readiness Levels, as clarified in the following sections.

1.16 Societal Readiness Level

The Societal Readiness Level has been originally proposed by the Innovation Fund Denmark⁵³, and was introduced to assess the level of societal acceptance of a certain technology. The intuition behind this dimension is that any innovation -be it technical or social -requires a certain level of integration in the societal environment. Thus, the higher the SRL, the more such an integration of the technology within the societal environment is established, or the lower the need for designing and implementing measures for promoting a transition towards societal acceptance. As such, the SRL is analysed by assessing the readiness of the society to adopt a technological or social solution. According to Innovation Fund Denmark the SRL has nine possible stages, which are reported in Table 6 with amendments from the original list as presented in Bruno (2020)⁵² and some slight modifications adjusted to fit the VITALISE project context.

Table 6 Societal Readiness Level

Maturity Level	Description
SRL1	Identification of the generic societal need and associated readiness aspects
SRL2	Formulation of proposed solution concept and potential societal impacts; appraisal of societal readiness issues; identification of relevant stakeholders that could act as agents of change towards increasing social awareness
SRL3	Initial sharing of the proposed solution with relevant stakeholders (e.g., through visual mock-ups, or presentation of prototypes or through LLs idea generation activities) - a limited group of the society knows about the solution or similar initiatives and offer initial reflections
SRL4	Solution validated through pilot testing in controlled environments to define proposed impacts and estimate societal readiness: a limited group of the society experience the solution by testing it or participating in relevant co-creating techniques
SRL5	Solution validated through pilot testing in real or realistic environments and by relevant stakeholders: the society knows the solution or similar initiatives but is

⁵² Bruno, Ilenia et al. (2020). Technology Readiness Revisited: A proposal for extending the scope of impact assessment of European public services. ICEGOV 2020: 13th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Electronic Governance Athens Greece September 23 - 25, 2020

⁵³ Innovation Fund Denmark. 2018. Societal Readiness Levels (SRL) defined. Retrieved February 2019 from https://innovationsfonden.dk/sites/default/files/2018-08/societal_readiness_levels_-_srl.pdf

	not fully aware of its benefits
SRL6	Solution demonstrated in real world environments and stakeholders are involved to gain feedback on potential impacts: the society knows the solution or similar initiatives and awareness of the solution benefits increases
SRL7	Refinement of the solution and, if needed, retesting in real world environments with relevant stakeholders: the society is completely aware of the solution's benefits, a part of the society starts to adopt similar solutions
SRL8	Targeted solution, as well as a plan for societal adaptation, complete and qualified; society is ready to adopt the solution and have used similar solutions that might already be on the market
SRL9	Actual solution proven in relevant societal environments after launch on the market; the society is using the solution available on the market

Based on the above table the connection between the TRL and SRL has an analogy, while the solution assessed may be technical or non-technical (at least partly). The first two levels, SRLs 1-2 reflects the growing awareness of a Research and Development team about the existence of a societal readiness issue. In turn, SRLs 3-6 are concerned with the more and more extended inclusion of societal stakeholders (such as prospective users or other similar groups) in the testing, validation and demonstration phases of the Research and Development outputs. Then SRL 7 matches TRL 7 in its being referred to the final stage of prototyping, while SRLs 8-9 is related to the pre-market and market launch phase of the solution.

1.17 Legal Readiness Level

Similarly, to SRL the Legal Readiness Level (LRL)⁵⁴ is a maturity model aimed to assess the potential legal or regulatory implications of bringing to market innovative solutions in terms of compliance but also the power to transform existing regulations towards a new era forged by new technological achievements. It is a fact that no innovation can reach the market if it is against the current rules that govern a specific domain. However, some breakthrough innovations can foster the configuration of new spaces for legitimate action. The higher the LRL score, the higher is the compliance level with the pertaining rules or the lower is the need to set up some measures to promote a transition towards legal compliance. The LRL has nine possible stages, which are reported in Table 7 with amendments from the original list as presented in Bruno (2020) and with slight modifications adjusted to fit the VITALISE project context.

Table 7 Legal Readiness Level

Maturity Level	Description
LRL1	Generic consideration of legal and ethical compliance aspects are observed but nothing has yet been done for the development of the solution to be in full compliance with current regulations
LRL2	Formulation of the need to enhance the legal normative, laws, rules and guidelines and solution concept; appraisal of legal and ethical compliance issues
LRL3	Abstract description of the proposed solution's legal and ethical compliance
LRL4	Solution's legal and ethical compliance prospects validated against any required

⁵⁴ Bruno, Ilenia et al. (2020). Technology Readiness Revisited: A proposal for extending the scope of impact assessment of European public services. ICEGOV 2020: 13th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Electronic Governance Athens Greece September 23 - 25, 2020 .

	or recommended changes in the legal and/or regulatory system
LRL5	Definition of the proposed solution’s legal and ethical compliance status after pilot testing in real or realistic organisational environments
LRL6	Detailed description of the required or recommended changes in relevant laws, regulations, or organisational rules to ensure full compliance with the proposed solution
LRL7	Refinement of the solution within the existing legal and ethical system and, if needed, proposals for required or recommended changes to some aspects of it
LRL8	Targeted solution, as well as a legal and ethical compliance audit, complete, qualified and ready to be launched on the market
LRL9	Actual solution proven legally and ethically compliant after launch on the market

The LRLs 1-2 match the SRLs 1-2 in reflecting the growing awareness of a research team about the existence of a legal and ethical compliance issue. LRLs 3-6 are concerned with the more and more extended consideration of laws, regulations, ethical principles and organisational rules in the testing, validation, and demonstration of the targeted solution. LRL 7 matches the same score of SRL and TRL in its being referred to the final stage of prototyping, while LRLs 8-9 belong to the pre-market and market launch phase.

1.17.1 Application of the VITALISE adaptation to the KTH Innovation Readiness Framework

As mentioned above, the main Innovation Management tool that will be used during the Assessment phase of the Innovation Management strategy of VITALISE project is the Innovation Radar. The use of the Innovation Radar Methodology will be complemented with the KTH Innovation Readiness Level™ Model, which allows the monitoring of the current development status of a business concept, and the planning of appropriate next steps towards increasing the maturity of a business concept. This approach is in line with the project’s innovation strategy that has been presented within the framework of D1.6 “Innovation strategy (first version)” and is summarized in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5. Summary of the Innovation Management Strategy of VITALISE Project

Some initial considerations on the potential benefits of the proposed modified KTH framework i.e., enriching the six dimensions included in the KTH tool with two more: **a)** a social readiness dimension,

and **b)** a legal readiness dimension stem from its being:

Respectful to the fact that many projects or TA/VA researchers may have already been evaluated based upon IR/MCPI framework.

Attentive to the combination of contextual factors in the environment that pertains when a new technology is introduced i.e., a new technology may not be easily introduced in a market or easily transferred to other similar contexts unless societal and legal /regulatory variables are controlled.

Compatible with a wide variety of solutions (technological or non-technological), although further adaptation may be required in the generalized descriptions of the scale to fit a specific project.

Verifiable as in the TRL, since the proposed SRL and LRL along with the other six domains included in the KTH Tool include high level descriptions that are adaptable and enable comparability.

Scalable on a micro and macro level, because many research projects in VITALISE can be monitored simultaneously, but also because of the ability to add dimensions if necessary for better depicting the commercialization potential of research projects within LLs globally.

The VITALISE Innovation Monitoring System will be assessing the commercialization potential of the research results for the Transnational and Virtual Access Research of the VITALISE project.

For Innovation Management to be effective, a responsible person will manage all activities related to innovation, from market need through capturing the IP to market deployment. Within the framework of VITALISE Project, this process falls under the responsibility of the **Innovation Management (IM) team**. The Innovation Management team has a central role in the entire innovation management lifecycle, as its responsibilities include key aspects like:

- Validating the innovation potential and innovation capacity embedded into the project.
- Facilitating an open dialogue among project partners to jointly understand concepts and processes related to innovation and up-scaling.
- Maintaining and updating (if needed) the innovation matrix of the project.
- Monitoring the project's progress to beware of potential risks against its key innovation elements, in order to take adequate actions to mitigate possible misalignment from the established plan.
- Provide advice on managing the Intellectual Properties (IPs) produced during the project
- Ensure that emerging innovations are adequately promoted and addressed by the dissemination and exploitation actions of the project.

The Innovation Management team consists of the two innovation partners of VITALISE project: VILABS and AV. More specifically, Anthology Ventures (AV) as an Angel-funded Startup Studio providing co-founder help in exchange for equity, along with access to finance from own investors for innovative teams, has demonstrated experience in evaluating innovative ideas in research and technology and provide support in the process of taking new innovations to the market. VILABS is an SME that acts both as a private research and innovation laboratory and as an innovation hub for startups. VILABS provides a wide range of research, development, and consulting services to national as well as international enterprises and organisations, utilising a unique set of tangible and intangible resources, including knowledge, facilities, human and financial resources, supporting researchers and entrepreneurs to innovate. Within the framework of the project, VILABS will exploit its extensive experience as an innovation leader and support the Innovation Management strategy and processes from the bottom up.

1.17.2 Role of AV and other partners in boosting commercialization potential

The role of AV and the other partners in boosting the commercialization potential of the research results deriving from the TA/VAs studies conducted during VITALISE, is to help researchers make

most of the access provided to the physical and virtual resources of LLs. The bootcamp will provide an overview of the business and start up principles, strategies and tactics that lead to commercialization increasing attendees' capacities in developing market fit products and business development. Increasing awareness of the attendees on the commercialisation tactics will help them capitalize on the experience and knowledge created during their access in the LLs by testing concepts or validating products within real life contexts.

In addition, AV can further support the commercialization potential of research results by providing access of promising research projects to business angels. AV apart from being a startup studio, it is also a business angel studio incubating micro-angels interested in providing initial capital to promising startup teams. AV is also well connected with a wide international network of investors, companies and organizations helping the funding cycle move forward syndicating rounds with other Angels and Funds. LLs may also support the access to capital capitalizing on their networks with Funding organisation or other business support organizations.

The bootcamp will guide entrepreneurs through the process of defining the necessary steps towards developing a newly founded company and offer know how to overcome lack of management and commercialization skills. The bootcamp will also help researchers as prospective entrepreneurs in developing leadership and management skills.

Researcher and entrepreneurs usually do not have the network required for building and scaling their business successfully. During the bootcamp researchers will be able to identify and leverage key individuals competences that may contribute to the success of their start-ups. Consortium partners i.e. Anthology Ventures, ENOLL, TREBAG, VICOM, CERTH, SIT, UPM, WITA, VILABS, LLSA as well VITALISE'S LLs, and RTOs can provide access to a wide network of stakeholders in the quadruple helix (public authorities, community, academic institutions and RTO's, and industrial actors).

Monitoring the development of TA innovations

To successfully monitor the development of innovation and commercialisation potential of TAs and VAs research projects, VITALISE has developed a fit for purpose monitoring action plan. Initially, the researchers selected to participate at the first bootcamp (T4.6) during the Open Living Lab days 2022 (that will be organised on 20-23 Sept. 2022) will receive the innovation and commercialisation evaluation framework along with relevant guidelines and will be encouraged to conduct and submit a self – assessment exercise along with their application. The approach will also provide insights on the innovation maturity level of each research project, and as consequence inform the bootcamp organizers (AV) to refine the training materials (if necessary, see Bootcamp training material, Annex C) to better match the needs of the target audience. In case that researchers selected to participate at the TAVAs will not be able to attend the bootcamps, then the self-evaluation innovation and commercialisation framework will be forwarded to them with relevant guidelines, while the bootcamp training material will be available through the training repositories on the teams channel of the project that will be created for the Summer School i.e., T4.2 and T4.3.

During the bootcamp, an analysis of the preliminary results will be presented along with an explanation of the evaluation framework. The 2-day bootcamp training materials and workshops are designed to analyse and tackle aspects relevant to the VITALISE innovation and commercialisation framework, thus providing an overview on methods and techniques to help researchers defining their tactics towards commercialisation processes. In coordination with the Innovation Management team (see Deliverable 1.6) and the Research Infrastructure Responsible (RILs), which will host the TA research activities and offer the VA support to researchers, researchers participating in the TAs and VAs will be asked to complete the VITALISE innovation and commercialization framework before the starting period of either the TA or the VA and at the end of it. Researchers will be encouraged to use the framework within three months after they finalise their TA or VA research in order to monitor their performance towards market reach, assess how their project has matured and refine their tactics, if necessary.

The VITALISE Innovation monitoring system will also be shared with the researchers selected to participate in the TA and VA after the second and third Open Calls (see D11.1) i.e., November - December 2022 and May-June 2023 respectively. The framework will be complemented with guidelines and the bootcamp material will be available in digital format. Research projects will be evaluated again for a second time at the end of the Transnational and Virtual Access periods i.e., May-September 2023 for the second bunch of TA (first bunch of VA), and November-January 2024 for the third bunch of TA/ VA (second bunch).

A time-plan for the monitoring of the TA / VA innovation and commercialisation potential is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Time-plan of the Innovation and Commercialization Evaluation Framework

Exploitation and sustainability plan

1.18 Creating and maintaining the right conditions for boosting commercialization potential

Living Labs are recognized as an innovation platform through which innovative solutions are tested, validated, and developed in co-creation with end users facilitating the innovation and commercialization process^{55,56}. By synchronising the innovation process with stakeholders via the Quadruple Helix Model, Living Labs support researchers in building competences and competitive advantages for realizing products and services in real life contexts from the idea generation stage, up to the commercialisation stage. However, the literature indicates that Living Labs' services focus more on: a) improving policy related initiatives and especially refining smart specialization strategies⁵⁷, b) provide networking and capacity building, c) support project planning and management, c) offer market and competitor intelligence services, d) facilitate co-creation, testing

⁵⁵ Buhl, J., von Geibler, J., Echnernacht, L., Linder, M., 2017. Rebound effects in Living Labs: opportunities for monitoring and mitigating re-spending and time use effects in user integrated innovation design. *J. Clean. Prod.* 151, 592-602.

⁵⁶ Leminen, S., & Westerlund, M. (2019). Living labs: From scattered initiatives to a global movement. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 28(2), 250-264.

⁵⁷ Lorenzo Compagnucci, Francesca Spigarelli, José Coelho, Carlos Duarte, Living Labs and user engagement for innovation and sustainability, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 289, 2021, 125721, ISSN 0959-6526, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125721>.

and validation for refining new products and getting feedback before launching to market⁵⁸, although relatively less attention is paid to a structured support towards commercializing new products or services^{59,60}.

Commercialisation activities generally aim to introduce the innovation to potential buyers and assess its market attractiveness. Commercialization is directly linked with adoption of an innovation referring not only to the process of creating but also the process of using the innovation. Adopting innovations is dependent on the a) learning conditions, referring to the attainment of new competences required to use the innovation; b) social conditions, explaining the cultural specificities of the user; and c) technological conditions referring to the explanation of the technical features of the innovation. It is therefore of critical importance to understand that an innovation that is being implemented is adopted and used by the users.⁶¹ We therefore adopt the definition of Datta et al.⁶² and we define commercialization as the capacity to bring a product to the market and reach the mainstream of the market beyond the initial adopters.

According to Datta et al. the commercialization process requires skills and entrepreneurial effort on the following thematic areas: a) identifying the sources of innovation, b) design a market entry strategy (requiring capabilities and feasibility), protection, development, and deployment.

In the context of Living Labs, the sources of innovation are the research and development conducted within real life contexts instead of constructed lab environments, and the multiple stakeholders that can be involved within R&D including government bodies, universities, research organizations, citizens, and industry. These can favour the development of innovations as alliances and collaborations among those actors can help bring entities closer i.e., networks with potential customers and suppliers are valuable sources.

Assessing when it is the right time for product launch may play a catalytic role in the success of the product. Certain steps can help in assessing the right time and conditions to launch into a market. Some of the strategies include the a) pre-launch period, where posts, ads and promotions can engage customers and/or b) attract customer interest with pre-launch product testing and getting feedback. Before the market launch however it is important to know and understand customer preferences and competitor's potential launches, i.e., some businesses prefer to launch as second movers instead of first movers, as waiting until the demand grows sufficiently and customers are familiar with a certain innovation can provide benefits.

Protection issues are also important in terms of how quickly competitors can imitate the launched product. Intellectual Property aspects need to be assessed and protection actions need to be taken at the right time in order not to delay market launch or diffusion about the product.

The process of developing an innovation within the living lab context can help maximize the possible fit with customer requirements, minimizing time to market and controlling development costs by involving a) customers helping to match the product with their specific needs and b) suppliers ensuring also that inputs are of appropriate quality, while helping in minimizing cost.

Deployment is mainly linked with the decision to sell the innovation or license it, and compatibility or interoperability issues, i.e., whether the product is interoperable with other products (even third-party products) especially when it includes a software-based component. Penetration pricing will also determine how many customers may buy the product and therefore should be designed considering a) covering the costs required to produce the product, b) earn reasonable profit, and c) grow market

⁵⁸ Lee, S, Olson, D., & Trim, S. 2012. Co-Innovation Convergences, Collaboration and Co-Creation for Organizational Value. *Management Decision*, 50(5): 817–831.

⁵⁹ Lorenzo Compagnucci, Francesca Spigarelli, José Coelho, Carlos Duarte, Living Labs and user engagement for innovation and sustainability, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 289, 2021, 125721, ISSN 0959-6526, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125721>.

⁶⁰ Westerlund, M., Leminen, S., & Habib, C. 2018. Key Constructs and a Definition of Living Labs as Innovation Platforms. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 8(12): 51-62. <http://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/1205>

⁶¹ The Living Lab Methodology Handbook. Accessed online 23.03.2022 at: https://www.ltu.se/cms_fs/1.1015551/file/LivingLabsMethodologyBook_web.pdf

⁶² Datta, A., Reed, R. and Jessup, L. (2013), "Commercialization of innovations: an overarching framework and research agenda", *American Journal of Business*, Vol. 28 No. 2, pp. 147-191. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJB-08-2012-0048>

share while being cautious of the competitors' pricing.

We therefore conclude that creating and maintaining the right conditions for boosting commercialization potential of research results require researchers to be aware but also apply fit-for-purpose strategies and tactics early in the process of designing their research and increase knowledge and capacities in multidisciplinary topics i.e., management, strategy, entrepreneurship, economics, and marketing, while planning accordingly for having onboard the appropriate team capacities that will forge the design and application of the respective tactics. Living Labs can play a critical role in increasing the variety of competences required through relevant capacity building trainings and coaching with experienced business mentors.

1.19 Sustainability plan

The training material to be developed during VITALISE for the purposes of the bootcamp focuses on how to increase the commercialization potential of research results in the context of Living Labs. The training material will be delivered to attendees of the bootcamp and will also be included to the training material of T4.2 and T4.3 along with the summer school training material (T4.1). Micro-credentials certifying the learning outcomes of this short-term learning experience will be assigned based on the micro credential strategy decided to be adopted for the online training material of the VITALISE project (T4.2). The bootcamp material (ppts, notes, and guidelines on how to use various resources related to business development and growth), can then be used systematically by Living Labs for fostering commercialization potential during and after the end of the VITALISE project. Further means of exploitation of the bootcamp material as one of the VITALISE exploitable results will be presented in "Task 13.5 Exploitation, Sustainability and Business plan", which aims to develop an exploitation strategy and support the individual exploitation plans of the partners to secure the post-project future and long-term sustainability of VITALISE.

Conclusions, Risks, and next steps

This deliverable focused on describing the context of the bootcamps and presenting initial research conducted regarding existing framework for evaluating innovation potential. It also offered some preliminary adaptation of the currently available frameworks i.e., the KTH Innovation Readiness Level that will be used for developing the VITALISE Innovation Monitoring System (T13.3). The deliverable outlines the strategy and structure of the bootcamps, which will serve as a "compass" to direct the Innovation and commercialisation potential of the TAs and VAs assisting researchers to form strategies and tactics towards commercialisation. Overall, it is essential to encourage the LLs to enrich the services offered and reach beyond the research related support to provide business support services and encourage but also facilitate researchers to find their pathway to market.

The bootcamp training serves the purpose of preparing the researchers to conduct innovative research that has a high potential to reach the market. A training material pack has been developed and uploaded to the project's online folder in Teams⁶³ and a Google Drive folder⁶⁴. The material will be subject to refinements and updates upon the date of the bootcamp delivery and the final version of the material will be submitted along with the rest of the training material that will be developed for the Summer School in T4.2 and T4.3.

Successful implementation of the bootcamp is linked with the constant and close collaboration with the communication, exploitation, dissemination, technical and commercial management activities of the project. AV will coordinate the promotion and dissemination of the bootcamp events in synergy with VILABS. Potentials risks and barriers will be mitigated and a smooth pathway towards attracting researchers will be ensured. If, at any point in time, a bootcamp or evaluation framework-related risk emerges, the AV and partners involved in T4.6 will call for an immediate project management

⁶³ [https://aristotleuniversity.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/VITALISE-](https://aristotleuniversity.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/VITALISE-H20202/Shared%20Documents/WP4%20(ENoLL)/T4.6%20BOOSTING%20COMMERCIALISATION?csf=1&web=1&e=Yd4ICi)

[H20202/Shared%20Documents/WP4%20\(ENoLL\)/T4.6%20BOOSTING%20COMMERCIALISATION?csf=1&web=1&e=Yd4ICi](https://aristotleuniversity.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/VITALISE-H20202/Shared%20Documents/WP4%20(ENoLL)/T4.6%20BOOSTING%20COMMERCIALISATION?csf=1&web=1&e=Yd4ICi)

⁶⁴ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1K89rPyxrlUm91ppzbh1eUeJKRAoKb9X6?usp=sharing>

meeting to discuss possible measures to mitigate the alleged risk. A tentative list of some risks identified

Table 8 Tentative Bootcamp risks and mitigation measures

Description of risk	Impact	Mitigation Measure
Low number of participants applying to the bootcamp	Low	The bootcamp will be widely disseminated with the support of VILABS and ENOLL network i.e., the bootcamp will be promoted within the Open Living Lab Days Event webpage and the network social media channels.
Projects applied have low maturity level	Low	Applications will be evaluated in terms of certain criteria (i.e., team, sustainability, market, product, innovation) that indicate maturity potential.
Short bootcamp period with the risk of not including the time required for increasing skills towards commercialisation	Medium	The bootcamp training material will be provided in digital form along with the rest of the training material developed during other related tasks i.e., T4.1 Summer Schools. The training material will also provide specific guidelines for using the resources presented after the end of the bootcamp.
Results produced during TAVAs are not well exploitable	High	Some projects might be in the early conceptualization phase and may not have proved their validity as a market-fit product. The innovation evaluation framework (T13.3) prepared from AV will offer a self-evaluation tool for informing researchers about the status of the product on various business aspects. Researchers may build on that to design appropriate measures for boosting commercialisation.

Annex A: Innovation Radar Questionnaire

Note: the first 16 questions below are to be answered for **each** innovation the project develops (up to a maximum of 3 innovations).

- 1) Describe the innovation (in less than 300 characters, spaces included):**
- 2) Is the innovation developed within the project...:**
 - a) Under development
 - b) Already developed but not yet being exploited
 - c) being exploited
- 3) Characterise the type of innovation (only to be answered if 2b or 2c is selected)**
 - Significantly improved product
 - New product
 - Significantly improved service (except consulting ones) - New service (except consulting ones)
 - Significantly improved process - New process
 - Significantly improved marketing method - New marketing method
 - Significantly improved organisational method - New organisational method
 - Consulting services - Other
- 4) If other, please specify:**
- 5) Characterise the macro type of innovation (only to be answered if "under development" is selected for Q2):**
 - Product
 - Marketing method
 - Organisational method
 - Process
 - Service (non-consulting)
 - Consulting service
 - Do not know yet
- 5) Will the innovation be introduced to the market or deployed within a partner:**
 - a) Introduced new to the market (commercial exploitation)
 - b) Deployed within a partner (internal exploitation: Changes in organisation, new internal processes implemented, etc.)
 - c) No exploitation planned
- 7) If no exploitation planned, please explain why no exploitation is planned (answer only if 6(c) is selected)**
- 8) Is there a clear owner of the innovation in the consortium or multiple owners?**
 - A clear owner

- Multiple owners

9) Indicate who is the "owner" of the innovation: ...

10) Indicate the step(s) already done (or foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market (answer only if 6(a) is selected)

	Done	Planned in project	Not Planned	Desirable
1. Technology transfer				
2. Engagement by Industrial research team of one of their company's business units in project activities				
3. Pilot				
4. Capital investment (VC, Angel, other)				
5. Investment from public authority (national, regional)				
6. Business plan				
7. Prototyping				
8. Market study				
9. Demonstration or Testing activities				
10. Feasibility study				
11. Launch a start-up or spin-off				
12. Other				

11) If other, please specify

12) Indicate which participant(s) (up to a maximum of 3) is/are the key organisation(s) in the project delivering this innovation. For each of these identify under the next question their needs to fulfil their market potential.

Org1:

Org2:

Org3:

13) Indicate their needs to fulfil their market potential

	Investor readiness training	Investor introductions	Business Plan Development	Expanding to more markets	Legal advice (IPR or other)	Mentoring	Partnership with other company (technology or other)	Incubation	Startup accelerator
Org 1									
Org 2									
Org 3									

14) When do you expect that such innovation could be commercialised? (answer only if 6(a) is selected)

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 2 years
- Between 3 and 5 years
- More than 5 years

15) Have any of the project partners...

(only to be answered if "Done" or "Planned in Project" is chosen for 10.5 "Investment from public authority")

- a) already applied for support from private investors
- b) already applied for investment from public authorities
- c) Planning to start discussions with private or public investors

16) Which partners are in discussion with investors (or are planning such discussions)?

General Questions

(questions below are to be answered once in the project review, not for each innovation)

1) How does the consortium engage end-users?

- End user organisation in the consortium
- An end user organisation outside of the consortium is consulted
- No end user organisation in the consortium or consulted

2) Are there in the consortium internal IPR issues that could compromise the ability of a project partner to exploit new products/solutions/services, internally or in the market place?

- yes

- no

3) Please provide specifics of the IPR issues:

4) Which are the external bottlenecks that compromise the ability of project partners to exploit new products, solutions or services, internally or in the market place?

- IPR

- Standards

- Regulation

- Financing

- Workforce's skills

- Trade issues (between MS, globally)

- Others

5) Indicate how many patents have been applied for by the project: _____

6) Does the review panel consider the project performance in terms of innovation?

- Exceeding expectations

- Meeting expectations

- Performing below expectations

7) General observations of innovation expert on this project's innovation performance:

8) How would you rate the level of commitment of relevant partners to exploit the innovation?

- Very low

- Low

- Average

- High

- Very High

- None

9) Please indicate the 1 partner (excluding large enterprises) that the panel considers to be the most impressive in terms of innovation potential:

10) Please enter some tag words (comma separated) to represent what "innovation elements" are strong in the project:

11) Please enter some tag words (comma separated) to represent what "innovation elements" can be improved (or are absent) in the project:

Annex B: The KTH Innovation Readiness Level

Table 9 Customer Readiness Level

9	Widespread product sales that scale	Widespread product deployment, sales to several customers in a repeatable and scalable way.
		Customer creation- company focuses on execution with growth of sales and efforts to build user/customer demand etc.
8	First products sold and increased structured sales efforts	Customer qualifications are complete and initial products are sold to a few customers.
		Payment willingness confirmed from sufficient % of customers (product-market fit validated).
		The real buyers/economic decision makers are identified.
		Business development and sales mature and adapt to support larger scale sales efforts (e.g. clear sales process/organization, CRM systems etc)
7	Customers in extended product testing or first test sales	Customer agreements in place- first sales and/or test sales of product versions take place (customer validation to show initial product-market fit).
		Customers and relevant stakeholders engaged in product qualifications/extended testing.
		Ramp up of business development and sales efforts according to sales process and roadmap.
6	Benefits of the product confirmed through partnerships or first customer testing.	Testing of product by customers/users where the value and benefits of the product is confirmed (validated problem-solution fit).
		Partnerships formed with key stakeholders in value chain (e.g. partners, pilot customers).
		Initiated structured business development/sales activities. First sales process/roadmap defined
5	Established interest for product and relations with target customers.	General interest from customers/users for the product where the possible product/solution (core features) is confirmed to solve customers' problems (i.e. initial problem-solution fit)
		Existing contacts strengthened and/or more contacts established with additional customers. Deeper understanding of the market is achieved. Target customers are identified
		Established relationships with potential target customers, users or partners e.g. providing input on requirements and initial prototypes (e.g. resulting in updated product hypothesis).
		Defined who the target customers/segments are to be focused on as entry/first customers.
4	Confirmed problem/needs from several customers or users	Contacts and feedback are established with several possible customers/users. Numbers are typically limited but depend on B2B/B2C and market structure (e.g. 5-10 in B2B, if market is concentrated 2-5 market leading customers, in B2C higher e.g. 10-20)
		The problem and need (and its importance) is confirmed from multiple customers/users
		Customer segmentation in place, knowledge of customers/users has increased level of details
		A primary product hypothesis is defined, possibly based on feedback.
3	First market feedback established.	Initiated customer discovery with feedback from primary market research i.e. direct contacts e.g. a few possible users/customers or persons with industry/market knowledge (experts)
		A more developed understanding of possible customers and possible customer segments
		A more clear problem hypotheses
2	Identified specific needs in market.	Some market research is performed, typically derived from secondary sources.
		Brief familiarity with the market, possible customers and their problems/needs.
		There is a more clear and more specific problem/need description
		Product/solution ideas may exist, but are not clear and typically speculative and unvalidated
1	Hypothesizing on possible needs in market.	Thinking (yourself) that a possible need/problem or opportunity might exist in a market.
		No clear hypotheses on who customers are and what problems are etc. If hypothesis exist they are unclear, speculative and there is no proof or analysis to support assumptions.
		Limited or non-existing knowledge of the market and customers/users (who they are etc)

D4.8 Commercialization Potential of Research Results

Table 10 Technology Readiness Level

9	Actual technology system qualified through successful mission operations	Actual application of the technology in its final form and under mission conditions, such as those encountered in operational test and evaluation
		Software: readily repeatable and reusable. The Software based on The technology is fully integrated with operational hardware/software systems. All software documentation verified. Successful operational operational hardware/software systems. All software documentation verified. Successful operational experience. Sustaining software engineering support in place.
8	Actual Technology system completed and qualified through test and demonstration	Technology has been proven to work in its final form and under expected conditions. In almost all cases, this TRL represents the end of true system development
		Software fully integrated with operational hardware and software systems, development documentation is complete. All functionality tested in simulated and operational scenarios.
7	Technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment	Prototype near or at planned operational system. Requiring demonstration of an actual system prototype in an operational environment (e.g., in an aircraft, in a vehicle, or in space). Normally only performed when the technology and/or subsystem is mission critical and relatively high risk.
		Critical technological properties are measured against requirements in an operational environment.
		Readiness in an operational environment requires evidence of The acceptable performance under operational factors, including, for example for a software system loading, user interaction, security etc
6	Technology demonstration in a relevant environment	Representative model or prototype system, tested in a relevant environment. Represents a major step up and requires evidence of performance on full-scale, realistic problems.
		For software: level at which the engineering feasibility of a software is demonstrated. This level extends to laboratory prototype implementations on full-scale realistic problems in which the software technology is partially integrated with existing hardware/software systems.
		Examples: testing a prototype in a high-fidelity lab environment or simulated operational environment.
5	Technology validation in relevant environment	Basic technological components integrated with reasonably realistic supporting elements so they can be tested in a simulated environment. Fidelity of breadboard technology increases significantly.
		Integrated components provide a representation of a system/subsystem for to determining concept feasibility and to develop technical data. Lab use to validate the technical principles of interest.
		Software: Module and/or subsystem validation in relevant environment. Ready to start integration with existing system, conforms to target environment/interfaces. System software architecture established and all components and elements affecting the operation of the critical software element.
		Examples: a new type of solar photovoltaic material promising higher efficiencies used in an actual fabricated solar array that would be integrated with power supplies, supporting structure, etc., and tested in a thermal vacuum chamber with solar simulation capability.
4	Technology validation in laboratory	Basic technological components are integrated to establish that they will work together. This is relatively "low fidelity" compared with the eventual system. System concepts considered and results from testing laboratory scale breadboard(s). Only limited and initial information about the end product function.
		Software: module and/or subsystem validation in a laboratory environment (i.e. software prototype development environment). Basic software components are integrated to establish that they will work together. Architecture development initiated (e.g. interoperability, reliability).
		Example: demo of a 'fuzzy logic' approach to avionics by testing algorithms in a partially computerbased, partially bench-top components to demo in a controls lab using simulated vehicle inputs.
3	Analytical and experimental proof-of-concept of critical function and/or characteristics	Active R&D is initiated to develop the technology/product further.. Analytical studies and laboratory based or experimental studies are performed to physically validate that analytical predictions are correct. Lab tests are performed to measure parameters of interest and compare to analytical predictions.
		Software: limited functionality environments to validate critical properties/analytical predictions using non-integrated software components and partially representative data.
		Example: super-cooled hydrogen as a propellant where the concept-enabling temperature/pressure for the fluid was achieved in a lab. Software algorithms run on a surrogate processor in lab environment.
2	Technology concept and/or application formulated	The potential technology/product concept is defined and described.
		Practical applications can be defined/ researched but are speculative and no proof or detailed analysis.
		Software: analytic studies, studies on synthetic date, small code units Example: observation of high critical temperature superconductivity, potential applications of the new material in instruments (e.g. telescope sensors) defined.
1	Basic principles observed	Published research that identifies the basic principles that underlie a technology.
		Scientific research begins to be translated into more applied research and development.
		Software: development of basic use, basic properties of software architecture, mathematical formulations, general algorithms. Example: studies of basic properties e.g. tensile strength as a function of temperature for a new material

Table 11 Business Readiness Level

D4.8 Commercialization Potential of Research Results

9 Business model is final and is scaling with growing recurring revenues that results in a profitable and sustainable business	Business model is final and Business is scaling with growing and recurring revenues.
	The business scales by growing in new markets, new geographies, new segments etc.
	There is a working Business which is profitable and sustainable over time.
8 Sales and metrics show business model holds and can scale. Business model is fine-tuned to explore more revenue options	Sales and other metrics show the business model holds and is profitable e.g. customer acquisition is not costing too much.
	The business model shows it can scale (potentially globally). Sales channels and supply chain are fully in place.
	Business model is set but is continuously fine-tuned to explore more revenue options.
7 Product/market fit and customers payment willingness demonstrated. Attractive revenue vs cost projections (validated by data and sales)	There is product/market fit meaning you can demonstrate significant customer interest and use of products and sales where customers show clear payment willingness.
	Attractive revenue vs cost projections (being validated by sales and data) implying a sustainable/ attractive business could be built.
	Preparations for scaling business with suppliers, sales channels etc (incl. agreements).
6 Full business model incl. pricing verified on customers (by test sales)	A complete Business model incl. The pricing is tested vs. customers by test sales or similar.
	The revenue model incl. pricing is updated and refined based on customer feedback.
	First more complete projections on revenue/costs (profit and loss projections or similar) with more details and well-grounded assumptions/data (e.g. 1-3 years horizon)
5 Parts of business model tested on market and canvas updated. First version of revenue model incl. pricing hypotheses. Verified competitive position/ uniqueness through market feedback	The Business model (at least parts of it) is tested against customers for verifying hypotheses.
	The Business model is updated and refined to new version based on customer feedback
	There is a first version of a more detailed revenue model incl. pricing hypotheses (what revenue streams are there, from what, when, how and what prices are possible?)
	The competitive position and differentiation is verified by market feedback.
4 First version of full business model in canvas (incl. revenues/costs). First projections to show economic viability and market potential	There is a full business model in canvas format incl. details on possible revenues/costs.
	First economic projections with numbers to show The market potential and economic viability (bottom-up calculations based on projections/guesstimates on volumes, prices etc)
	Assessed feasible Share of market based on e.g. barriers to entry incl. competition
	Made a competitive analysis on your position and uniqueness/differentiation vs them.
3 Draft of business model in canvas (excl. revenues/costs). Described market potential and complete competitive overview	There is draft of the business model in a canvas format (business model canvas/lean canvas) but typically without the revenues/cost parts and details of these.
	The market description is getting more highly resolved with more specific market applications and segments being identified. Target applications identified.
	The market potential and the market size is quantified with TAM and SAMSegmented/Served Available/Addressable Market (everyone you have decided/can reach)
	A more complete competitor overview with direct/indirect competitors and alternatives
2 First possible business concept described (e.g. NABC). Identified overall market and some competitors/alternatives	Described the proposed business concept in some structured form e.g. NABC
	One or several markets or applications are identified and described on overall level e.g. user numbers, TAM- Total Available or Addressable Market (everyone you wish to reach)
	Some competitors and/or alternatives are identified and listed
1 Hypothesizing on possible business concept. Little knowledge or insight into market and competition	Vague and unspecific description of the potential business idea or business concept
	Little insight into The market and its potential/size-hypothesizing on possible applications
	Little knowledge or insight into competition and alternative solutions

D4.8 Commercialization Potential of Research Results

Table 12 IP Readiness Level

9	Strong IPR support and protection for business.	Strong IPR support and protection for business, for example using various other forms of registered IPR (trademarks, designs etc) or for example using agreements, trade secrets etc.
	Patent granted in relevant countries and maintained in force	Patent granted and maintained in several countries relevant for Business
		Patent is in force/valid with No invalidation procedures
8	IPR strategy and IP management fully implemented.	IPR strategy is fully implemented and managed. IPR is proactively used to support business, for example all IPR related agreements are professionally managed and new IP is managed.
	More complete assessment of freedom-to-operate.	First Patent is granted with relevant scope for Business
		No oppositions encountered for Patent grant
7	All relevant IPR filed (e.g. additional patents).	Other forms of relevant IPR might be registered such as trademarks, designs.
	Patent entry into national/regional phase.	Entry into national phase (US, EU, JP etc.)
		Complementary or additional new patents might be filed
6	IPR/patent strategy implemented and supporting business.	More full IPR strategy in place that is validated by professional and that really links to and supports business strategy.
	Positive response on filed applications.	Patent strategy in place-identifying possible additional patents, country strategy, claim changes.
	Initial assessment of freedom-to-operate (or landscape)	Positive response on applications from authorities and analysis of response performed
		If no positive response: analysis is performed together with professional with strong arguments and strategy for prosecution.
5	Draft of IPR/patent strategy in place to use IPR for business.	Initial assessment of freedom-to-operate (e.g. competitor based, narrowed product scope etc.) or landscaping. Overall purpose to get knowledge on the field, key IPR, players and activity.
	Filed first complete patent application (or other IP registrations)	Draft IPR strategy- First analysis (preferably by professional) on how different IPR can be used to protect and be of value for the business.
		Patent strategy- professional analysis on what/how to Patent and how to improve/build value of patent application (e.g. supporting data, new/additional details to be filed etc.)
		Basic agreements in place to ascertain control of IPR (e.g. assignments, ownership copyright)
4	Confirmed if protection possible and for what (e.g. patentability).	First complete Patent application (or other IPR registration) filed in cooperation with professional
	Decided why to protect certain IPR (business relevance).	Confirmed novelty and patentability through searches/analysis by professional
		Confirmed possibilities for protecting other forms of IPR
		Possibly filed "provisional" Patent application i.e. not professionally drafted and complete
3	Detailed description of possible key IPR (e.g. invention or code).	Analyzed (ideally with professional) The key IPR and what The priorities should be for what to protect (e.g. patent). Decided on alternative forms of protection if patents are not suitable.
	Initial search of technical field and existing IPR.	Considered what forms of IPR are key and could/should be protected (e.g. through patents)
		Sufficiently detailed description of possible IPR and patentable inventions (invention disclosure)
		Made own searches/analysis of publications, state-of- the art solutions etc.
2	Identified different forms of possible IPR that you have.	Possibly initial searches by professional to find prior art within Patent databases
	Ownership is clarified and you clearly own/control IPR.	Mapped different forms of IPR that exist or could emanate during development
		Specific ideas for patenting exist, but are not well described and defined.
1	Hypothesizing on possible IPR you might have (such as patents, software, copyright, designs, trade secrets etc.)	Agreements related to IPR are identified and ownership is clarified. IPR is verified to be under your ownership or control. Inventors are clarified. Knowledge of applicable IP policies etc.
		Hypothesizing results or ideas might contain possible patents or Some other form of IPR
		Some ideas on IPR e.g. for patenting may exist, but are speculative and uniqueness etc. not clear.
		Vague description and documentation of The possible IPR
		Limited knowledge or unclarities regarding relevant legal agreements (ownership, use-rights etc.)
		Limited or non-existing knowledge of the technical field, state-of-the art, publications etc

D4.8 Commercialization Potential of Research Results

Table 13 Team Readiness Level

9 High performing well-structured team and organization that is maintained and performs over time	The team is high performing and well-functioning (cooperation, social environment etc).
	The team is motivated, coached and rewarded to reach goals. Team-building is active.
	Strong culture, a clear and functional structure (organization, roles etc) exists with processes etc.
	The team is maintained and developed and performs over time
8 Management and CEO in place. Professional use of board/advisors. Activated plan and recruitment for building long term team.	Personnel is developed and trained professionally according to a more long term strategic plan.
	There is a clear leadership and management. CEO in place with relevant business experience.
	There is a competent board which is professionally used. relevant advisors are in place and used.
	Necessary recruitments according to longer term plan are ongoing to ascertain competencies
7 Team and culture is fully in place and proactively developed. Updated plan for building necessary team on longer term.	The team is properly motivated and rewarded so everyone performs at their max.
	culture is formed and used to develop and support The team and company development
	The team is well aligned with shared goals/vision and The team is well functioning with clear roles
	The team is proactively developing their skills, cooperation etc. and there is a plan for this.
6 Complementary, diverse and committed team with all necessary competencies/resources incl. both business and tech.	Some additional recruitment needs might exist. e.g. a new CEO or key technical Personnel
	There is a plan for necessary recruitments and needed resources over longer term (~2 yrs)
	Complementary team in place with technology and business as well as team diversity.
	Committed team where everyone is feeling responsibility and accountability.
	All key competencies Necessary for The near term are present.
	Advisors (e.g. advisory board) and/or board members are considered and recruited.
5 Initial founding team with main needed competencies. Team agrees on ownership and roles and has aligned goals	Low dependency on a single individual for specific key skill or expertise
	Awareness of risks to team performance (internal conflicts, politics, conflicting agendas/priorities)
	Initial recruitment and other activities for securing competence/resources completed successfully.
	An initial founding team working together and all spending significant time. The founding team jointly having main needed competencies
	Additional team aspects e.g. background and diversity are considered (e.g. balance male/female)
	Recruitment or network activities to ascertain additional persons/resources are progressing
4 A champion is present. Several needed competencies in place. Initiated plan for recruiting or securing additional key resources.	The team has agreed on their respective shares (signed agreement). Ownership is balanced and incentivizing and reflects historical and future commitment and contribution.
	The team is aligned with clarified roles, shared goals and clear commitment (e.g. time spent)
	A champion (driver and Committed to take The project forward) is present in The team
	Several, but not all, competencies necessary are present, typically multiple individuals in team.
3 A few of necessary competencies/resources are present. Defined needed competencies/resources (and plan for finding).	A plan is in place and initiated to recruit persons with defined needed skills (described e.g. in a requirement profile). Activities initiated for ascertaining key resources in e.g. partnerships.
	The team has started discussions on ownership as well as roles and commitment going forward
	A few of the necessary competencies/resources are present. One or several individuals that possess some, but not all, of necessary competencies/resources.
	The existing and needed competencies/resources have been defined and gaps to fill identified.
2 Insight and first idea on necessary competencies or external resources (e.g. partners).	An initial "Team plan" is put in place for what is most needed near term (<1 year) and how to
	Some insight that additional necessary competencies and/or resources (e.g. partners) are needed
	First idea on what additional persons, competencies and resources that could be needed
1 Little insight into the need for a team (typically an individual). Lack of necessary competencies/resources.	Limited competencies present- typically an individual.
	Little insight into needed/necessary competencies (knowledge, skills) and other needed resources (e.g. partners, service providers etc)
	Typically an individual lacking the necessary skills in key areas such as technology, business etc.
	No consideration or interest to build a team with additional and complementary skills

Table 14 Funding Readiness Level

9	Investment obtained.	Investment formally concluded with all relevant documentation and money obtained.
	Additional investment needs and options continuously considered.	Additional future investment needs and options are continuously being Considered for future
8	There is corporate order and structure enabling investment.	The company is reasonably structured e.g. in terms of agreements, ownership (not fragmented or significant parts held by inactive/non-contributing persons) etc. There is formal order in the company e.g. bookkeeping, documentation etc.
	Term sheet discussions with interested investor(s).	Clear interest and discussions (on term sheet level or similar)with interested investor(s)
		All necessary material often required by investors in place (financials, business plan)
		Concrete discussions with One or several possible investors that clearly are interested.
7	Team presents a solid investment case incl. status and plans.	There is a team that can present well the investment case where key areas are in place such as prototype, traction/customer interest, market potential with scalability etc. There is a complete Business plan with financials and milestone plan etc in place
	Discussions with potential investors on-going around an offer.	Discussions with potential investors are on-going around a defined offer (how much money, for what, conditions, valuation etc)
		There is alignment amongst existing team and owners with a shared view on investment
6	Improved investor presentation in place incl. business/ financials.	There is an investor pitch deck that has been tested and fine-tuned and which includes a focus on the business potential and financials to attract investor interest.
	Decided on seeking private investors and initial contacts taken	Insight into equity financing especially how investors think/evaluate, investment criteria etc.
		Decided to pursue equity funding and take in new owners.
		Decided on a First offer to private investors i.e. amount/valuation and use of funds
5	Investor oriented presentation and supporting material tested.	There is an investor presentation (pitch deck) that has been tested and is being fine-tuned. Supporting material e.g. financial projections and budgets etc. are being developed
	Applied for and secured additional larger funding (soft or other).	Applications for other types of funding e.g. grants or loans are prepared and filed. Larger soft funding
		Insight into the basics of equity financing and willingness to consider it, i.e. no major fear of losing control/ownership.
4	Good pitch and short presentation of the business in place.	A succinct pitch (oral) and good written presentation of business concept is in place
	Plan in place with different funding options over time.	There is a more complete plan for funding needs/options over time (12-18 months) i.e. overall budget and potential sources of funding.
3	Well described business concept and initial verification plan.	Well described business concept and initial verification plan (incl. hypothesis to verify, goals)
	First small soft funding secured.	Basic insight and knowledge of different financing options Obtained first small soft funding for commercial verification according plan
2	Description of business concept (e.g. NABC).	The business idea/business concept is reasonably well described incl. first version of value proposition (e.g. NABC). The business concept is not verified and updated
	Defined funding needs and funding options for initial milestones.	The initial funding needs are mapped for initial key steps and milestones i.e. costs/budget There is a basic plan with funding options for initial milestones (3-6 months)
1	Initial business idea with vague description.	Initial business idea with unclear/poor description- no value proposition (e.g. NABC)
	No clear view on funding needs and funding options.	No insight into how much funding needed and for what. Little insight into different funding options and funding types.